

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION

BETHOVEN M. FILOMENO

**NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS BRANDING ON A DIGITAL PLATFORM:
AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY**

Thesis Adviser:

JEAN A. SALUDADEZ, PhD

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

12 August 2023

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **BETHOVEN M. FILOMENO** with the title: “**Non-Profit Organizations Branding Practices in a Digital Platform: An Ethnomethodological Study**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Development Communication (MDC)

JEAN A. SALUDADEZ, PhD
Chair, Thesis Committee

August 12, 2023

(Date)

ALEXANDER G. FLOR, PhD
Member, Thesis Committee

August 12, 2023

(Date)

MELINDA F. LUMANTA, PhD
Member, Thesis Committee

August 12, 2023

(Date)

DIEGO S. MARANAN, PhD
Dean
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

August 12, 2023

(Date)

Biographical Sketch

Bethoven M. Filomeno is an academician with almost 20 years of teaching experience both in Manila, Philippines, and the United Arab Emirates. Currently he is a Faculty for Media, Culture and Communications and Course Leader for Innovation Modules at Westford University College in Sharjah, United Arab Emirates.

A graduate of both Bachelors and Master of Arts in Education at the Philippine Normal University Manila, aside from being in the teaching field, he is also a creative media practitioner focusing on film and media production, photography, design thinking, visual and fashion communication. His passion in both the academic and media fields made him recognized and hailed as one of the 300 Most Influential Filipinos in the Gulf in the year 2020 by *Illustrado Magazine* under the Thought Leaders category, and he recently received an award in Excellence in Teaching Profession in Higher Education – GAWAD PINOY 2023 by The Filipino Social Club. His creative works in photography and writing got published in various international magazines such as *Vogue Italia*, *Vogue India*, *Harper's Bazaar UK*, *Mega Magazine Philippines*, *Egalite Magazine* in Mexico, *Bengaluru Chronicles*, *Out and About Magazine* and *OFW Premiere Magazine*. He is also a contributing editor for *Victor Magazine*, a Dubai based lifestyle magazine.

He is also involved in various academic-related events and conferences where he served as conference speaker on teaching innovation and session chair in the recently concluded Best Practices in Teaching and Learning Conference organized by American University of Sharjah, Amity University Dubai, and Khalifa University. His passion in teaching and

the creative media industry paved the way to open doors for him to be interviewed and land a feature in the Global Filipino Magazine where he is recognized as one of the excelling Filipinos in the Gulf and featured in an article entitled: An educator and advocate making waves in the creative media production.

Acknowledgement

The success of this thesis would never be possible without the guidance of the Lord Jesus Christ Almighty. His presence in my life is the most important guiding light for me to fulfill this faith goal. My strength and willpower to continue comes from him alone.

I would like to thank my thesis adviser Dr. Jean Saludadez, for her never-ending support and guidance in helping me build my thesis from day one. Her patience and passion to guide me resulted in the success of my study. To my research committees Dr. Alexander Flor and Dr. Melinda Lumanta for providing valuable input to improve my work, I totally appreciate everything. To our program leader in MDC Dr. Benjamina Paula Flor for guiding us all since we started in 2019, her leadership and motherly love and concern made an impact to all of us in class. And, to the MDC support team for assisting me with all the queries and concerns.

This academic journey will not be possible without the presence of my classmates to whom I owe you the encouragement and strength to continue. To start with, I would like to thank Cleofi "Tita C." Capili as we both journey on this MDC program together since day one in 2019 and worked together is some of our TMAs. To my overseas classmates based in the US and Singapore, Vida, Julie, Mike, Cristel, Chloe, and MJ I am very thankful for the friendship that we built along the way and helped us all to finish this race.

To my friends and mentors here in the UAE who contributed to the success of my MDC program. To Dr. Fazal Malik who encouraged and mentored me to pursue my academic

career path in the media and communications field. To Albert Versoza, Wilbert Sayson, Seigmond “Mang Emong” Abad, Louie Da Costa, Danielle Francisco, Dr. Rex Bacarra, Dr. Jan Fernando Reyes, Ms. Jo-C Conlu and the Love Company and to my students Chirag Patel, Edwin Job, Hasaan Al Shawki and Vamsi Putta your contribution in my academic journey is much appreciated.

And to my other group of friends my Victory Dubai Spiritual Family for standing with me in prayer, Amity Mafia friends, Malobago Sisters, my DSE International family and M5 Friends thank you so much for supporting me all the way.

And finally, I thank my family for being there always to support and encourage me that I can be the best person I can be and to continuously strive for more. To the Magante and Filomeno clan. My siblings, sister-in-law, nephews, and nieces. Kuya Barry, Eva, Micah, Agatha and Ameera. Jericho Vir, Grace, Gab, Zach and Migs. Jonah Gil, Rowena, and Jacob. You are all such an important part of my success. And most importantly to my parents, whom I firmly believe are very proud of all my achievements and the success that I have. This another milestone is proof of my love for both of you, I offer this to you Mama Beth and Papa Benjie.

Dedication

I dedicate this study to my family, friends, mentors, academicians, students, and communications industry leaders, as well as the thriving diverse community of the United Arab Emirates which served as my second home away from home for the past 9 years. This marks another successful season of my academic and professional life and will continuously strive for more to become an agent of change and source of inspiration for the next generation of leaders.

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ABSTRACT

NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS BRANDING ON A DIGITAL PLATFORM: AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY

Non-profit organizations are entities whose aim is to set programs and initiatives for the benefit of the public. Conducting research on non-profits in branding establishes a robust identity that fosters elevated levels of trust, support, and engagement among its primary stakeholders, namely the public. In terms of communication, it creates and establishes a unique position that contributes to the organization's long-term success and impact. This research aims to explore the branding practices done through public relations of a non-profit organization in Dubai using social media and to discover what intent these practices accomplish. Additionally, the purpose of this study is to provide insights to communication practitioners and stakeholders on the value of branding in various activities and engagements. As a research framework, ethnomethodology was used, and this study utilized the qualitative research method specifically using a conversation analysis (CA) approach.

The study centered around a non-profit organization situated in Dubai, whose identity has been anonymized in line with ethical research considerations. The data enclosed within brackets was extracted from the organization's social media platform, specifically their Facebook Page. This data encompassed three distinct types of social media content: video reels, infographics, and images. The conversation between the author and followers from each post was analyzed using the principles of conversational analysis (CA). The organization employed a range of branding techniques through public

relations, leveraging social media. These practices encompassed strategies such as content publishing, public affairs, and publicity efforts. These findings indicate that there are more possibilities for communications industry practitioners to improve and discover new approaches to communicate important information and campaigns, as well as open ideas to evaluate current practices to develop programs for government and private entities globally.

CHAPTER I

RATIONALE

Branding is about creating an identity and perception. It is a story based on the organization's mission and vision. As discussed by (Saygın, 2023), it entails forming a unique reputation and identity for a company or an organization among its stakeholders. To be able to communicate the branding and image of an organization requires public relations. Public relations or PR is one of the branches of communication that is deeply involved in the creative and strategic process of information dissemination. As mentioned by (Dixon, 2017), it is also considered as the lifeblood for many companies and organizations, but it can be a challenging field to master. Operating within the business sector, its primary objective is to cultivate, sustain, and enhance an appreciation of various segments within the public sphere (Nikolic et. al, 2016). However, this field is said to be in a theory crisis. As discussed in (Sisco, 2013), despite the scarcity of published research, the past six years have witnessed a considerable surge in the volume of scholarly articles, although only a few pertain to advanced levels of study. Because of this gap, this study aims to explore the branding practices through public relations of a non-profit organization using social media. This chapter will introduce the study through a brief discussion of its background and context, and its relevance to the body of knowledge.

Branding and Public Relations

The field of branding and public relations are always considered as intertwining disciplines, as they both deeply involved in the communications process. As discussed by (Mikáčová, 2014) enhancing the awareness of the public and their commitment to a brand through public relations is a usual practice. It is an essential part of any overall strategy

that aims to sustain and raise the standards of performance and credibility of an organization. It is where the foundation of communicating one's identity in the public sphere starts to grow and evolve. As it progresses, branding proves that public relations are a strong bond of discipline. In the study of (Szondi, 2010), it states that public relations can contextualize branding initiatives and create a favorable environment for overall strategic branding projects. On the other hand, the concept of public relations and building a brand is being represented as a tool of communication. In the study conducted by (Cardoso et. al, 2020), branding has become a key tool in the practice of public relations in finding out perceptions of people in managing their own identity and building their personal brand. In the realm of communication campaigns and initiatives, both public relations and branding emerge as pivotal forces, firmly establishing themselves as key players within the industry. As mentioned by (Long, 2006), branding and public relations should be viewed as assets and key tools in campaigns, aiding in the attainment of the objective to execute a process that encompasses constructing an organization's identity, fostering public awareness, and positioning the entity itself. In essence, each discipline possesses distinct key attributes, yet they share a common objective: to proficiently convey identity, programs, and initiatives, thereby fostering a productive and harmonious connection between the public—primarily the principal key stakeholder—in various endeavors, whether within the private or public sector.

Public relations and the non-profits

The public relations industry and nonprofits play very important roles in disseminating information and communicating initiatives for society. As examined in the

study by (Polić, 2019), communities establish non-profit organizations with the aims of providing care for the vulnerable, advocating for civil and equal rights, and seeking innovative avenues to express their advocacies. On the other hand, public relations, as discussed by (Mikáčová, 2014) is one of the communication fields that is designed to craft and preserve an organization's image and relationship to the public. In his research (Mitchell, 2012), observed that in the context of public relations for sustainable development within non-profit organizations, the Warm Heart Foundation in Northern Thailand adopts a Public Relations for Community Development philosophy. This underscores a noteworthy collaboration between these two entities and practices, though there is a suggestion for enhancing its execution to bolster the sustainability of its programs. With this result, it only shows that even if there is a program for the organization, there should be strong follow-up and focus on the implementation of the set goals.

To be able to show the effectiveness of the program and target the goal, one of the common and most sought-after PR practices is creating campaigns. In a study conducted by (Polić et al, 2020), it was revealed that the public relations communication campaign undertaken by a specific foundation in Croatia, focused on children, successfully augmented its recognition within both national and local media across the country.

While this outcome generated a favorable influence, the study also decided that local media ought to play a more active role in bolstering the organization's campaign, thereby aiding in the realization of children's aspirations, and rallying public support for the initiative. This scenario shows that even if there is a strong partnership between PR

practices and the organization, other sectors also need to give strong support to fulfill the goal. Another study which focuses is on a waste management initiative conducted by (Nmere et al., 2020), was able to discover that the PR campaigns of the non-profit organization resulted in public enlightenment. The strategy had a significant influence on the way people followed the waste management process, which also shows that there was effective community participation.

Conversely, their study highlighted a distinct finding: an imperative to enhance media involvement in championing the campaign, with a focus on educating and stimulating a broader audience reach through a combination of conventional and contemporary media platforms. Both studies revealed that indeed, campaigns organized by public relations teams and non-profit organizations were able to reach their goals, yet they needed extra support from other stakeholders to have a more sustainable implementation of their programs. Regarding engagement in these initiatives, a study examining our roles as community and board members (Waters, 2007) disclosed that a significant portion of community members routinely employ public relations to forge connections within the community. This revelation further unveiled that these individuals also assume the role of public relations representatives in strategizing for the organization's future development. But, unfortunately, even though there were members that actively participated, there were still sizable number of members mentioned that didn't have any involvement in the efforts. From (Waters', 2007), study, it reflects that there should be more push and encouragement for members of the public to take part and to mobilize them in fulfilling the mission of whatever cause it will be. From public involvement, another important focus of the public relations and non-profit organization collaboration is

the skill and devotion that it requires from its workers. From the research of (Dixon, 2017), it was discussed that the biggest difference working with a non-profit organization and other types of companies is that the person needs to make sure that they are focused on the mission of the organization. This loyalty to the job and the organization's mission will lead to a more effective implementation of the organization's activities.

Additionally, (Dixon, 2017), mentioned that communication skills and creativity in both technical and practical aspects are necessary. Skills in dealing with stakeholders in marketing, campaigns and even the design part are a must. These findings reveal that doing public relations for non-profits is a serious business and that a person should be holistically prepared and equipped to perform his/her duty to their best. The amalgamation of the skills possessed by individuals behind the scenes and the active engagement of the public will culminate in a more empowered and impactful effort to effectively communicate the brand of a specific organization and its array of programs. As public relations are concerned it is necessary to build a strong brand. In the study by (Sandell, 2012), the results showed those organizations that use public relations as a practice were able to build their brand successfully at a rapid pace. It further underscored the significance of incorporating public relations in the process of devising and upholding a robust brand.

From these sets of previous studies conducted by researchers from different years, in which public relations and non-profits are concerned created an understanding that they both exist and perform well together given proper attention and with a strong support system from stakeholders involved. It proved that the practice of public relations can

create a strong movement to build a powerful brand given the right mindset from skilled practitioners and the involvement of the public. The field of both public relations and nonprofits is significant in nation building.

They collaborate and perform key strategies to reach their stakeholders and to establish sustainable relationships with them. As stated in (Polić, 2019), public relations support and supplements the work and initiatives of non-profit organizations by spreading the word and scope of their work to attract and encourage public participation and to foster further sustainable development of the community and the society.

Public relations and social media

Social media occupies a significant role within the realm of public relations, functioning as a pivotal practice within the broader communication field. Research in this domain is abundant and multifaceted, presenting an array of perspectives offered by diverse authors and experts within the sphere of public relations. To make a point and set a good review of present literature, the discussion will be in chronological order from the year of its creation and publication. This will allow us to form an understanding on how social media use in public relations evolved throughout the years.

To commence, the research carried out by (Damasio et al., 2012) asserts that social media plays a pivotal role in establishing the base of the PR pyramid, offering the potential to serve as a cornerstone for shaping organizational experience, strategy, and conceptualization within the realm of development communication. From this perspective, (Damasio et al. 2012), discussed how the model of the PR pyramid highlights a significant

role in public relations as an orchestrator of organizational communication that transcends interactions between social media platforms and its stakeholders. If their study highlights public relations as an orchestrator, another study points out another distinct yet equally significant facet of knowledge. The research made by (Stockhausen, 2014) indicated that public relations effectively generated essential themes, highlighting the emergence of social media as an exceedingly valuable communication tool.

The findings elucidate that the concept of opportunity is embedded in the utilization of social media within public relations, which is perceived as a cost-effective tool. It also allows for the education sector to use it for social awareness, (Stockhausen, 2014), also highlighted that it provides a larger and more youthful audience and most importantly it facilitates real time conversation and engagement with its users. While these aspects signify advancements and opportunities, the study also uncovered themes of challenges associated with the utilization of social media in the realm of public relations. It was mentioned that it is time-consuming and causes privacy and confidentiality concerns. In the case of a non-profit organization, he pointed out that the directives of the organization might cause negative reactions and responses in the public without proper development of content, as the common mindset and perception is that public relations for non-profit organizations is always about donations and volunteering. Though this mindset of other people is hard to break, a study by (Ngoso, 2018) shed light on the idea that social media serves the real functions of public relations which is to properly communicate. The programs and initiatives of the organization. As social media provides useful information dissemination, the study conducted by (Nugraha et. al, 2019), pointed out that social networking sites represent high potential for increased interaction between various

sectors of the community, government, and stakeholders in the PR industry. Having this observation from the PR landscape, there are other observations from other studies that reveal information that allows the industry to consider improving skills and practices in general.

While these aspects signify advancements and opportunities, the study also uncovered themes of challenges associated with the utilization of social media in the realm of public relations. (Kamel et. al, 2019), mentioned that non-profit organizations in Egypt use social media mainly for narrow benefits but lose its real value to mobilize and build the community mo. In contrast to the earlier study, the research conducted by (Santoso, 2020) unveiled that PR practitioners possess the capability to facilitate two-way communication between the organization and its constituents. Thus, public relations using digital media is closely related to the use of social media. Its role is to establish good relations and create cooperation with the public.

Talking about the public as one of the stakeholders, it was highlighted in the study made by (Tong, 2021), that there was significant positive correlation between the PR practitioners use of social media as a strategy and their perceptions of interactivity experiences by the stakeholders when using whatever social media platforms of a certain organization. This proved that both parties collaboratively work together for a common goal which is for organic human interaction. To support this argument and claim, the study by (Morshed et.al, 2023), discussed that interactivity and humanizing interaction with stakeholders on social media pages can increase engagement to make a certain brand strong. In this context, social media gives organizations greater opportunities to

communicate with their audiences because it truly provides them with a chance to be in a more humanizing voice when communicating, being who they are and speaking their organic self.

Concluding this exploration of the interplay between public relations and social media, it becomes evident that both avenues offer numerous advantageous outcomes, as well as areas for enhancement, when employing this strategy to engage with stakeholders. Understanding its strengths and weaknesses will allow public relations practitioners to see the gaps, bridge them with a proper mindset and provide solutions. At the end of the day, this partnership between the practice and the platform will evolve and continuously thrive and will face innovation to promote sustainable communications strategies for the benefit of the public. Numerous studies in this area of public relations and nonprofits exist that pertain to their relationship and how they deliver programs and activities in a collective and collaborative manner. One of which is the study conducted by (Nmere et. al, 2020), wherein it reveals that nonprofit public relations practices have a significant influence and impact in the government's waste management program. However, these studies limit their focus to traditional media and other significant specific practices that are not present in the study. This body of knowledge has illuminated a gap, highlighting the need to delineate the public relations practices of non-profit organizations within the framework of social media utilization, and to ascertain the extent to which this practice contributes to the development of their organizational brand. Additionally, another gap is that most of the studies are focused in Southeast Asian and African countries and few focus on the Middle East. Consequently, the current body of research exhibits a gap in knowledge regarding the precise public relations strategies implemented

by these organizations, along with their intricacies. Furthermore, there is a dearth of information on the execution of these practices, the outcomes achieved through social media communication tools, and a particular focus on non-profit entities situated in the Middle East, particularly the United Arab Emirates. In this juncture, conducting this study will help bridge these identified gaps by particularly identifying public relations practices stemming from the sets of social media interaction and conversations between the identified non-profit organization and the public.

This study will also allow us to discover how these practices are being executed through various social media strategies that will be identified along the process. This study will also serve as mediator between the practices and their accomplishments that will stand as a strong foundation in building a new body of knowledge in the field of public relations, research, and academia. And finally, conducting this research in the Middle East setting will provide a different perspective and will show different discoveries in terms of strategies and implementation of programs, as the region has a different sets of practices and guidelines in this field. The significance of this research lies in its potential to offer a comprehensive vantage point within the realm of public relations communication and the non-profit sector. By meticulously examining all facets of social media activities and associated initiatives, this study aims to fulfill its primary objective of bridging the existing gap between practice and outcome. Ultimately, the study seeks to unveil the achievements and evaluate the efficacy of leveraging these strategies in fortifying the organization's brand identity. This study will add value to the field of development communication research as, although there are diverse studies around,

they lack focus on the public relations industry and nonprofits. Aside from the industry, this will also help the research field and practitioners to pursue topics related to this field and will discover a new body of knowledge that can help building new strategies in the field of research and the public relations industry.

In the realm of research, this study is poised to serve as a benchmark and a valuable resource, informing the formulation of effective strategies across various domains, including marketing, advertising, and public relations, within this region. Furthermore, it holds the potential to serve as a comparative reference, assessing its effectiveness and applicability, thereby offering insights that can be adapted and replicated in diverse global contexts. Overall, both the industry, academia and research fields will benefit from this study as it will open doors of opportunity for all. And as research it will only matter if it mirrors the past, is applied in the present and helps navigate the future.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter undertakes a comprehensive review of distinct literature sets, which collectively establish a robust framework for the study's contextual underpinning. It draws substantiation from a multitude of themes, concepts, arguments, and concluded insights derived from prior research conducted by fellow scholars within the realm of communication. This will add to the ever-growing studies in the field of communication, particularly the public relations field. (Sisco, 2013), concluded that, despite the lack in research published on this topic, the last 6 years has evidenced a notable increase in the number and proportion of scholarly articles about public relations. However, this should by no means deter researchers from continuing to explore novel discoveries within the multifaceted domain of public relations. The literature review is structured into three distinct sections. Firstly, it delves into the comprehensive essence of public relations, serving as the focal point of the study. Subsequently, it explores the realm of public relations engagements within the government sector, acknowledged as a collaborator with non-profit organizations in the advancement and mobilization of their initiatives and programs. Lastly, the review scrutinizes the utilization of social media within non-profit organizations. These groups of concepts and themes will build a strong foundation to set the pace of understanding the topic and to bridge the gap between studies that are already researched and new knowledge that will arise as the study progresses.

Public Relations

This section provides an overview of studies made about public relations which is a general term used to describe a communications practice that deals with communication

information, initiatives and dealing with public affairs in relations with media and the communications sector. The practice of public relations is very broad and applicable in almost all types of industries. As a communication field it's deeply involved in the creative and strategic process of information dissemination. Nikolic et al. (2016) focusing on the PR activities in various companies in Serbia, defined Public Relations as a strategic communication process that aims to create, maintain, and promote mutually beneficial cooperation between organizations and their environment. Another study conducted by Mikáčová (2014) that relates PR in branding, states that it is designed to craft and preserve an organization's image and relationship with the public. It is also considered as an activity in business that has its focus in establishing, maintaining, and developing an overall understanding of different segments in public (Nikolic et al., 2016). Conversely, it is also regarded as an alternative manifestation of a marketing strategy, necessitating a structured approach to influence both the public and targeted stakeholder groups, while concurrently offering services to the public (Lloyd, 2015). In the broader context, public relations transcend being mere tactical business tools. As highlighted by (Gregory, 2010), public relations involve not only the transmission of information but also the enhancement of its presentation. It is an important and integral part of a process in strategic development that is grounded on thorough-going research and skilled analysis of set objectives. Within the realm of public opinion, public relations demonstrate its capacity to realize diverse objectives, encompassing activities such as increasing awareness about specific issues and persuading individuals to undertake specific actions (Zoric, 2016).

Public relations and the government

One of the sectors where public relations is much required is the government sector. (Duhalm et al., 2010), concluded that public relations serve the purpose of cultivating and sustaining a government's environment that fosters comprehension, cooperation, and effective communication with the public. This finding sets a good example of how the organization's credibility and honesty can be communicated by public relations practices. However, in a broader context, challenges and concerns faced by government entities are rarely devoid of obstacles. Yet, as affirmed by (Duhalm et al., 2010), the presence of public relations can facilitate a significant accomplishment: the restoration of government credibility in the eyes of the public. Additionally, they added that activities such as foundations and charity organizations that are being supported by governments require public relations expertise to raise funds and acquire advanced methods of lobbying to fulfill their mission to serve the public (Nuffus et al., 2022) reached the conclusion that the government public relations efforts within a specific energy ministry of a country achieved effectiveness by ingeniously presenting information, employing novel media formats to enhance the appeal of communication. In their case the use of Instagram was able to build a strong relationship with the public. Such findings support another research study result from (Garba et al.2022), which is set in Nigeria. Their discussion revealed that both national and sub-national governments maintain a range of two to six social media accounts to reinforce their government public relations initiatives. However, despite this range, it was evident that the utilization frequency remains notably limited due to certain constraints. This underscores the necessity for government employees to be better equipped with adeptness in contemporary forms of communication and public relations practices that encompass digital media technology.

Another example from this context is the study by Irwanto et al. (2022), focusing on the socialization activities of the government. The results show that public relations play a significant role in implementing their program internally using social media. Other findings revealed by Irwanto et al. (2022), were that there are constraints being faced by public relations in disseminating government programs through social media. This reflects the same concern that there should be a rigorous equipping session for government employees to learn the latest trends in new media communications. This concern should not only be put on the shoulders of the government but more so to public relations practitioners in government sectors. The responsibility of stepping up is necessary. In the study conducted by (Bashir, 2019), set in a Middle Eastern country, it was revealed that some public relations professionals demonstrate a low level of adherence to the basic principle of excellence.

This study also revealed that there is less involvement from this practitioner in the strategic management planning in the government office. This resulted in another finding that there is a lack of qualified PR practitioners to support the government in communicating its programs and initiatives. Upon reviewing these diverse studies conducted by various researchers, it becomes evident that public relations undeniably stand as an imperative for all government agencies. Serving as a conduit of communication, it effectively bridges the gap between these agencies and the populace, who remain at the heart of the government's focus and concern.

While undoubtedly a crucial facet within government operations, public relations

practitioners should prioritize enhancing their role by equipping government employees with fundamental PR skills. Additionally, staying abreast of the latest communication trends is of paramount importance. Furthermore, these practitioners must consistently engage in comprehensive planning, recognizing that they represent the government's voice to the people across all spheres of engagement.

Social media use in the non-profits

This last segment of the literature review will focus on the use of social media in the field of non-profits. As organizations, non-profits seek to continuously communicate and execute their programs excellently. With the rise of social media as the number one communication tool in the digital era, it is very important for non-profits to maximize the use of this communications technology. Research studies in the field talk about various practices and show findings that matter to support this research. As the primary objective of this study revolves around the utilization of social media within non-profit organizations, the comprehensive review of diverse studies reaffirms the notion that the collaborative relationship between non-profits and social media is poised to persist and thrive.

To begin with reviewing existing literature on this topic, (Lovejoy et. al 2012), argues that social media use in the non-profits has three key functions, which is to inform, build community, and put plans into action. (Guo et.al, 2013) supports this claim and suggests that social media is a powerful communication tool for non-profit organizations and is considered as a formidable “public education” approach in disseminating information on the organization. Drawing from the study conducted by (Guo et.al, 2013), it is proposed

that a two-dimensional perspective on communication within advocacy initiatives— frequently undertaken by non-profit organizations through social media—encompasses the examination of messages based on their fundamental communication structure and their direct alignment with the core mission of advocacy. This stems from the fact that social media mobilizes people to react and act on certain programs. People engagement is the ultimate successful outcome of a proper communication strategy by an organization. In this juncture, studies conducted by various researchers point out facts about public engagement. The study undertaken by (Cho et al., 2014) underscores that the public exhibits a heightened level of engagement with messages from non-profit organizations when two-way symmetrical communication is employed on social media platforms. If these findings show that public engagement is in a good state, there is a study that disagrees. Based on the research conducted by Galvez-Rodriguez et al. (2014), it was observed that the utilization of social media within certain non-profit organizations is relatively scarce, particularly in terms of generating content aimed at nurturing public engagement. These findings revealed several factors of significance. Network activity, internationalization, and proficiency in social media emerged as pivotal elements in mobilizing the public. Moreover, these factors are indicative predictors of the utilization of social media as a potent channel for communication and interactive dialogue. In contrary to the research findings of the previous study, research conducted by (Chiulli, 2014), pointed out that non-profit organizations began to utilize the social media platform as interpersonal communication as a continuous innovation process in the age of new technology. (Young, 2016), indicates that organizations are generally satisfied with their use of social media as a communication tool to promote their organizations programs and services. Though there are limitations in the resources and skills they plan to continuously

adapt with the changes and trends in the use of social media. Talking about limitations, social media is a technology-based innovation, and humans need to be abreast of changes and improvements. Studies conducted by researchers such as (Khan et. al, 2014), concluded that nonprofits should allocate human and financial resources to social media to strongly support their causes. This move should also be done alongside within a comprehensive strategic plan. (Lam et.al, 2020), revealed that more nonprofits that depend on private funding will likely use social media compared to those supported by the government.

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In this case, the finding revealed that, within the private sectors, support to nonprofits will create a higher possibility to build their strong brand with the use of social media. Another interesting body of knowledge connected to this theme of social media and nonprofits is the level of interaction between the organization and the public. (Tao et.al, 2021), discussed that there is a two-way interaction between messages and functional interactivity.

This interactivity causes involvement on different levels of behavioral outcomes, and this makes a strong claim that practical insights on when, how, and why nonprofit's use of social media communication is effective. On the other hand, one significant result in public interaction is the value of socialization. (Namisango et. al, 2021), states that there is a positive relationship within the use of social media in communicating initiatives to socialization and visibility. These factors positively bring the organization and the public to the practice of co-creation, which reflects a collaborative engagement between the two.

This, in effect, strategically describes that the practice of using social media for nonprofits is an effective means not only to communicate programs but more so to mobilize people to be part of achieving the organizations' goal. To close the loop for this theme, the knowledge and information pertaining to the practice of nonprofits in using this communications strategy, studies revealed that social media use is underpinned by five principles of dialogic communication (as proposed by Kent and Taylor from the findings of (Li et. al, 2022) study). These principles mentioned are mutuality, commitment, proximity, empathy, and risk. From these sets of principles, it is likely that non-profit organizations approach to the use of social media requires a thorough serious focus not only on the execution but also on the planning.

Lastly, (Vidak et. al, 2023), concluded that the use of social media is not only for communications purposes but also to show the transparency of their work. At the end of the day, even if the goal was achieved, if the necessary ethics and honesty is not there, the true meaning of fair and balanced communication is useless. This statement is an important consideration in the field of nonprofits. It is all about the heart to serve and the mission to be of help and support to the people. The line up of all studies discussed and reviewed overarches the fact that indeed the practice of nonprofits is holistic in nature. All aspects of life need to balance from both the practitioners, the organization and the stakeholders, The use of social media in promoting, delivering, and executing initiatives is an important tool that requires for continuous improvement and innovation from both parties. Understanding its value for the organization is a necessary step. And finally, its

partnership is unending, it will continue to evolve and transcend boundaries and will keep on thriving for a common goal of improving the lives of people.

The overall review of the studies conducted by various researchers in the field provided a strong warrant for the research topic. While not all findings yield favorable outcomes, the amalgamation of both positive and adverse results imparts a robust groundwork for exploring novel concepts that contribute fresh insights to the existing body of knowledge. It will also help in bridging the gap to some missing links between the public relations field, the practice of the nonprofits and the use of social media in delivering information and mobilizing the public to act and be part of change in their society, community, and the country.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

Ethnomethodology as Research Framework

This chapter will showcase a visual representation of the relationships between the involved theory, concepts and their connection to the research that will serve as a guide and the blueprint in answering the research aims and research questions. For this study, it will utilize the ethnomethodology approach. First introduced by sociologist Harold Garfinkel, ethnomethodology has sub fields that includes conversation analysis and ethnomethodological studies. At its core, ethnomethodology is a form of social theory that investigates how social orders are possible (Trace, 2015). This theory is interested in analyzing making sense of and understanding the inputs from actions and structures. On the other hand, ethnomethodology's means of making sense involves studying the nature of documents which creates deeper insights between the connections and relationships of people and the recorded body of knowledge stored in the different forms of documents. Based on the article of (Cole, 2005), natural documents, in the ethnomethodology lens, refers to the available sets of legal documents, recorded in various forms that includes signs, symbols, and texts. Within this compiled repository of recorded knowledge, an overarching significance is bound to emerge, facilitating a comprehension of the underlying social context. Referred to as documentary analysis, this approach serves as an evidence-driven method for substantiating the credibility and authenticity of the documents at hand. In the context of this study, ethnomethodology stands as the foundational framework, guiding the utilization of a process aimed at extracting meanings from the existing array of documents. Specifically, this pertains to the digital media

platform, particularly the social media page of the focal non-profit organization. This approach will facilitate the identification of the organization's public relations practices and their implementation strategies, thereby elucidating how they navigate social media to achieve their intended objectives of fostering a robust brand identity.

Utilizing this theoretical lens of ethnomethodology, all the practical activities involved in the process will contribute to discovering ideas that are not yet known and will turn into an empirical concept that will provide additional useful knowledge in the field of public relations and communications.

Research Framework

Figure 1

Ethnomethodology Research Framework

It is the utmost goal of this study to discover the public relations practices of the anonymous non-profit organization in Dubai using social media to build a strong brand. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

Research Questions

1. What are the branding practices of a non-profit organization on social media platforms?
2. What intent of non-profit organization do these branding practices accomplish?

CHAPTER IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter provides the full details of the different methods to be used for the study. Each research being conducted is different from one another and it has its specific requirement. This chapter will begin with the discussion of social media platforms Facebook and Instagram as the basis for the data source. Also, this chapter will provide a detailed justification of various key research design choices from its strategies, data collection and its analysis. It will also identify the different limitations of the study and will conclude with a comprehensive summary of the methods of the entire study.

Conversation Analysis

The study will be utilizing Qualitative Research Design to generate an in-depth and quality delivery of information about the focus subject of the study. As a research design, qualitative research is an umbrella term for a wide variety of approaches to and methods for the study of natural social life (Saldana, 2011). Specifically, it will undergo the process of Conversation Analysis (CA) in which the center focus is on in-talk interaction. Conversation Analysis is more than a methodology, it is also a paradigm under various disciplines that includes sociology, psychology, and linguistics (Flick, 2014). In the context of this study, the online interaction which is the data set is considered allowable in terms of analyzing online conversations that have been captured with no interventions or any manipulation from the researcher (Meredith, 2019).

Study Site: Facebook Page

This segment will focus on the demographics of the online interactions between the Non-Profit Organization chosen and its followers as the focus of the study. The following discussion will highlight the importance of the gathered data from the Facebook page post of the organization in line with the specific comments of the users and followers of the page. Social media's advent opened huge opportunities and new strategies for people to communicate using the internet. Its emergence has transformed communication dynamics between businesses and their stakeholders (Morshed, 2023).

Most organizations in different sectors use social media as their top communication strategy. In the 2013 statistics 70% of Fortune 500 organizations use Facebook and 69% are on YouTube (Beukeboom et.al, 2015). In the government sector, social media is also being utilized as one of the most effective means of communicating important information for the people. Local governments in every country, like any other organizations, have increasingly turned to the used of platforms like Facebook to interact and pursue online activities such as listening, watching videos, creating awareness, and providing customer service to people (Baltz, 2023).

In this case, social media platforms play a vital role in communicating brand awareness of organizations to their consumers both in the marketing, advertising, and public relations activities of the company. Out of all social media platforms existing in our generation, Facebook leads the way as the common and most popular platform being used by both individuals and organizations. A popular networking site, Facebook was

launched in 2004 and was invented by Mark Zuckerberg as a space for university students to gather on the web before it became popular and available to the public (Abd Rahman, 2018). With a burgeoning popularity boasting over 1.4 billion daily users, a consistent average for Facebook, this platform unmistakably empowers users to seamlessly share content, fostering stronger interpersonal connections among individuals (Abd Rahman, 2018). As an online entity, Facebook gives itself the chance and possibility for its users to communicate their thoughts and ideas, as well as creating idealized rather than true identities through their profiles (Nadkarni et. al, 2012). Being a potent social media platform, Facebook possesses a remarkable capability to amalgamate and harmoniously integrate an array of multimedia activities, setting it apart from its competitors (Baltz, 2023). This distinctive trait renders it captivating for both individual users and companies alike. The distinctive attributes enabling the creation of diverse content formats such as videos, images, events, statuses, and marketplace listings contribute significantly to its popularity among business owners and organizations. They leverage this platform for their operational needs, particularly in effectively communicating their activities, thereby fostering marketing and sales endeavors.

Among the most potent and promising aspects of Facebook is its Facebook Page, brimming with potential. Previously called fan page, Facebook pages exist as the same use and purpose as the personal profile wherein users and administrators can broadcast their point of view, create public presence and awareness using various multimedia such as image, audio, and videos (Hanna, 2023). It is a simple yet very strong Facebook vertical that allows individuals, organizations, and brand's content to be available to its users. Various brands create a paid account on Facebook page which is most frequently

used to communicate directly to consumers (Beukeboom et.al, 2015). The reach of Facebook brand pages is much higher than Facebook groups, with some brands maintaining brand pages with over 40 million (Red Bull) or even 80 million (Coca Cola) followers (Beukeboom et.al, 2015). As a result of its huge use another stronger version of the page is Facebook for business. With a Facebook page for business, users can accurately access their audience analytics, add a call to action or search for helpful applications and services. Liking, messaging, saving posts, sharing, and commenting are available on posts of Facebook pages (Hanna, 2023). The data collected from this study come from the Facebook Page of the chosen Non-Profit Organization in Dubai which aims to amplify stories about people living in the country and its vibrant diverse communities. The Facebook Page of the organization is the online place where users and followers usually participate through commenting and appreciating the postings of the organization for its various initiatives, activities, events, and announcements.

Data Collection

While numerous research method books and articles delve into the collection and compilation of data from online sources, there remains a notable absence of standardized procedures for conducting such activities (Meredith, 2017). Data gathered were those considered fitting for the type of study that is being undertaken. The uses of various approaches like participant observations, interviews, surveys, visual and textual analysis are some examples of the strategies. In the context of this research, a social media Facebook Page of a Non-Profit Organization in Dubai is the chosen platform to be analyzed as the main source of data.

As an online platform where social interactions are the main activity, this method aimed to understand how the users or people behind the screen interact with the postings of content of the organization as a means of their public relations practices. (Meredith, 2017) argued that if we want to understand how social interaction is organized online, then we need to examine the interaction in its actual occurring setting.

As discussed earlier in this chapter, the source of data will come from the Facebook Page of a Non-Profit organization in Dubai. Particularly from the postings of content and the conversation between the page owner which is the company's social media administrator and its followers. The organization's Facebook page has 125K likes and 478K followers which makes it a page with legitimate traction of activities from interaction and exchange of comments and replies with its followers. The organization's identity and its followers were anonymized for the purpose of safeguarding the privacy and confidentiality to promote trust and enabling the dissemination of valuable research findings without compromising the organizations or any individual's identities. Based on the various content and postings of the organization and since the organization has a huge content database, I specifically choose and bracketed three (3) different types of social media content: video reels, photos, and infographics image posts, to see the differences of interactions and conversations of the followers and to discover how these types of content serve as useful and effective public relations communication tools.

Through the diversity of media content, the brackets used will serve as the basis for the overall data analysis. The study deals with the online interaction and conversations

of the Facebook Page owner which is the non-profit organization in Dubai and its followers. Prior studies addressing similar data have employed an array of approaches and methodologies to execute and present their research findings, given the absence of a standardized transcription method (Meredith, 2014). Managing the data is a tedious process that deals with lots of considerations along the way. The process began by carefully checking the Facebook page of the organization and getting the feel of the traction of the conversations between the content author and its followers.

As mentioned on the previous discussion, due to a large number of contents that was posted, I have decided to choose three (3) distinctive social media posts of the non-profit organization, wherein each content represents a diverse delivery of information for the public. As part of the initial process, there are steps that I followed to be able to organize and manage the data carefully for the benefit of a well-structured data gathering.

First, I had to **do a screenshot of the social media post** as my reference of the author and followers' interaction and conversations. The process was done to all the three (3) types of content that was mentioned previously, video reels, photo, and infographic image. The screenshot material provided a holistic characterization of both the textual and visual data required to understand the traction of conversations. The image below shows one of the samples of a social media content that serves as the data source for this study.

Figure 2
Facebook Page Video Reel Post from the chosen non-profit

After the screenshot image has been captured, the **second step is the process of organizing the textual data** followed by doing a rundown of the conversation sequence to secure my own understanding of the structure of the turn taking of comments and replies which is the focus of conversation analysis. Based on the process of scrutinizing the structure of the data sets I was able to come up with my own strategy of organizing the data by creating my version of turn taking and sequence flow of the conversation using a data flow diagram that will support to manage the management and analysis process. The diagram for all the three (3) content type will provide a visual and textual representation of the conversation flow.

Figure 3

Diagram that represents the conversation flow from the video reel post.

Figure 4

Diagram that represents the conversation flow from the infographic image post.

Figure 5

Diagram that represents the conversation flow from the photograph post.

This process of formulating the diagrams from the different social media content post of the non-profit organization's Facebook Page created a more organized means of understanding the chosen data. The three diagrams exhibit both commonalities and distinctions in terms of turn-taking and the sequential flow of the conversation. This intriguing information warrants in-depth analysis. During the process of formulating the diagrams, I was able to identify initial ideas on how the throw of comments and replies creates successful and meaningful information that will beneficially affect the results of the study. Consequently, the diagram was formulated by focusing on the author's original post with its caption and hashtags. The date of the post was also identified as it provides an important segment of the analysis. Each of the comments and replies was represented by direct line connections and some broken line that represents its relationship to the original author's post. All the comments and replies were represented by the date and time stamp which is a very significant part of the conversation. Certain diagrams display gaps, including filtered comments intentionally set by the author or deleted by followers. These omissions are noteworthy and hold potential significance for future analysis and progression. The placement of each box of comments and replies represents how each one of them are interconnected by visually representing its sequence and its relationship to one another. The usage of numbers on the left-hand side represents the line-by-line analysis of sequence along with sub numbers on each comment and reply to boxes.

As a component of the process, the **third step** I undertook involved the **meticulous line-by-line encoding of the textual content derived from the online conversation**. This entailed the manual encoding of every line encompassing social

media posts, comments, and corresponding replies within the conversation. As part of the ethical process, as mentioned previously, I anonymized the identity of the organization and the followers by using words, letter and number codes that represents each of them, such as the word *Author* for the creator of the post which is the non-profit organization and using the letter *F* and a particular number to represent the followers who commented and responded to the post. This stage was approached as an iterative process, allowing me to navigate back and forth between the transcripts for thorough examination and analysis. Sample of the line-by-line coding of transcript is represented below.

Figure 6

Line-by-Line coding of the conversations between the Author of the post and the followers who are commenting and replying on the post.

```
1 Author's Post: Is Dubai Metro CLEAN? #dubai #challenge #dubailiving #cleanestcity #dubaimetro
2 F1 - Germs/bacteria and viruses can't be seen in a simple wipe.
3 It looks clean, tidy, but it's not 100% clean.
4 Author: F1 I dunno about you, but the fact that we wiped it and
5 no dirt? That kinda speaks volumes.
6 F2 - Author it's hard to please sister 😊
7 F3 - F1 exactly
8 F4 - F1 para sa public transpo with 1M passengers everyday, it is
9 considerably clean ghorl...and the video didnt
10 mentioned that its "100% clean"...i bet even ur house isnt that clean...kelangan pa ba
11 nagmicroscope sila?juskolord 🤔🤔🤔
12 F1 - F5 opinion ko, i won't change it because sabi mo. I'll post
13 mine; you post yours.
14 He looks clean, but I doubt that there will be no bacteria left behind, because of the crowd
15 on board.
```

This strategy of using the diagram and line-by-line coding creates a more productive process of managing and organizing the data available for analysis. Overall, the process is tedious and takes time, but this is a very helpful and necessary process to

follow for a more effective data analysis. Afterwards, the next step is to finally analyze the data using Conversational Analysis (CA).

And finally, the **last step** and the most important part of the methodology is **coding the extracts and assigning codes** that highlights the branding and public relations practices and accomplishments of the organization based on the extract of the conversations from the three different types of social media content. Each extract underwent an initial analysis, encompassing an evaluation of its contribution to the overall conversation flow. Subsequently, the main theme and sub-themes of each extract were identified and delineated. Subsequently, specific codes were applied to accentuate the discerned practices unveiled within the conversation. These codes were then followed by additional codes that corresponded to the nature of the accomplished practice. Consolidating them together, a common pattern was identified from both the branding practices and accomplishments of the organization that leads to formulating an overall general analysis from each extract of conversation. The resulting table provided a concise and structured summary of the analysis, encompassing themes and codes derived from the extracts. This compilation proved highly valuable in effectively identifying the requisite concepts necessary for achieving the research aims, objectives, and addressing the specific research inquiries. In essence, comprehending the data gathering process affords a comprehensive insight into the operational dynamics of the selected non-profit organization's Facebook Page. This pertains specifically to the interactions and dialogues among followers in response to the organization's online social media posts. This will

establish how the data was gathered, managed, and organized for the authenticity and for an organic measurement of the interaction that took place in the Facebook Page as the platform of choice. It also described the strategy used on how the data will be more understandable for the purpose of data analysis and it also provides information about the ethical process used to anonymize the sample.

Data Analysis

This study aims to explore the branding practices of a non-profit organization on social media platforms. With this goal in mind, the process of analyzing the available set of bracketed data will undergo an approach of conversation analysis (CA) which has a long history of interest in the role of technology in interaction (Meredith, 2019). Conversation analysis (CA) is more than a methodology. It is also a paradigm under various disciplines that includes sociology, psychology, and linguistics (Flick, 2014). Within the framework of this study, the online interactions, constituting the dataset, are deemed permissible for analysis. These online conversations have been captured without any interventions or manipulations by the researcher, aligning with the methodology outlined by (Meredith, 2019). The bracket of data set from the Facebook Page postings of the organization allows its followers to interact with all the information that is publicly available to everyone, and this relationship provides a direct communication between the organization and the public. Given this contextual backdrop, the interactions present a valuable opportunity to rigorously scrutinize the practices of branding and public relations through the lens of social media.

To show the flow of interactions and conversations that represent the idea, the following figure will provide a direct discussion of the analysis.

Figure 7

Video reel post from the Facebook page of the organization with interactions and exchange of comments and replies from followers.

Extract 1

- 1 Author's Post: Is Dubai Metro CLEAN? #dubai #challenge #dubailiving #cleanestcity #dubaimetro
- 2 F1 - Germs/bacteria and viruses can't be seen in a simple wipe.
- 3 It looks clean, tidy, but it's not 100% clean.
- 4 Author: F1 I dunno about you, but the fact that we wiped it and
- 5 no dirt? That kinda speaks volumes.
- 6 F2 - Author it's hard to please sister 😊
- 7 F3 - F1 exactly

Examining the structure and progression of the conversation stemming from the initial post by the organization, it is evident that their aim was to gauge public sentiment concerning the cleanliness of Dubai Metro. The author's opening statement in line 1, framed as a question, clearly indicates their intention to solicit the public's viewpoint on

the presented content. In addition to the question, the author strategically employs various hashtags to enhance the post's visibility among a broader audience. Hashtags such as *#dubai #challenge #dubailiving #cleanestcity and #dubaimetro* will get more traction and attention to the social media world.

With the author's post, it is obvious and expected that its followers will interact with what has been shared and this type of content is open for public opinion. Follower 1 = F1 commented on the author's original post with a response in line 2 and 3 with a combination of almost agreeing and most disagreeing tone of voice. On lines 4 and 5, the author responded with a reply challenging F1 about his/her comment. This form of conversational exchange exemplifies one of the key findings in Conversation Analysis, known as Turn Taking. Theoretically, Turn-taking was introduced as a fundamental concept within Conversation Analysis (CA), aiming to describe the typical patterns observed in spoken conversations. This principle, applicable even in online conversations, dictates that individuals engage in speaking sequentially, taking turns to contribute to the dialogue (Farina, 2020). Following the conversation on line 6, another follower which is F2 replied to the author's comment by supporting the authors that F1 is a type of person that is hard to please followed by a laughing emoji that represents either sarcasm or just making the conversation more interesting for the readers and followers. The interaction illustrated in the sequence of the author's post, F1's comment, and F2's reply distinctly exemplifies another crucial concept within Conversation Analysis, known as Adjacency Pairs. In CA, an adjacency pair encompasses two sequential turns, where the initial turn establishes an anticipatory context for the

succeeding turn (Moshavi, 2021). This conversation shows that from the original author's post, there are 2 followers who commented with different opinions about the main topic, this leads me to conclude that it effectively serves as a successful approach to capturing the public's attention towards a specific concern or significant topic within the country. Continuing with the analysis, on line 7 another follower, who is F3, responded by replying to F1's comment on the author's post which shows that the person agrees with F1's comment. F3's response exemplifies another fundamental discovery of CA known as Transition Relevance Place (TRP), which involves a pattern where a speaker chooses the next participant to provide a response. In this case F3's action of replying to F1 signifies that he/she wants to get more interaction with F1 which can also be a way for the author and maybe other followers to react in his/her response that shows that F3 has many options about who to reply to and will second the motion with the response given.

Continuation: Extract 1

8 F4 - F1 para sa public transpo with 1M passengers everyday, it is
9 considerably clean ghorl...and the video didnt
10 mentioned that its "100% clean"...i bet even ur house isnt that clean...kelangan pa ba
11 nagmicroscope sila?juskolord 🤢🤢🤢
12 F1 - F5 opinion ko, i won't change it because sabi mo. I'll post
13 mine; you post yours.
14 He looks clean, but I doubt that there will be no bacteria left behind, because of the crowd
15 on board.

In the following lines, which are line 8 to 11, another follower responded to F1's comment that explains the real daily scenario of the public transportation system in the country. With F4's explanation using numerical values such as 1M represents a million of passengers, the follower wants to highlight that in the case of Dubai's public transport system it is already clean. She followed it up using 100% clean to represent and to agree

with most of the followers' opinion. F4 also uses ... to represent that he/she wants to say more to prove his/her point of view and uses question marks to compare the cleanliness of the Dubai metro to the cleanliness of a house which was used as a sarcastic example and with the use of microscope which signifies another mocking respond for F1's comment followed by three laughing emojis that makes the statement wittier.

F1's last group of replies from lines 12-15 shows a response from a missing follower's identity which is represented by F5. F1 shares that his / her opinion will not change and followed with a statement that as a person he/she will post whatever opinions he/she wants to share on the online platform. Lines 14 and 15 is where F1 points out more of the explanation backing up his/her claim based on the first comment that he/she put in the author's original post. This exchange serves as an illustration of CA's core attributes, encompassing Turn-Taking, Adjacency Pairs, and Transition Relevance Place. As expounded by (Moshavi, 2021), CA is best perceived as one among a range of data analysis methodologies that can be effectively employed to examine social interactions, as seen in the context of interactions and discussions within this specific social media post.

Figure 8

Infographics Image post from the Facebook page of the organization with interactions and exchange of comments and replies from followers.

Extract 2

- 1 Author's Post Dubai is giving FREE Covid 19 vaccination! Get yours now!
- 2 Download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA for your appointment. #NOappointmentNOentry
- 3 Thank you, UAE, for prioritizing the health and safety of citizens and residence alike!
- 4 And look! Truly, Emirates loves Philippines, sign at vaccination center has Filipino translation!
- 5 CENTER FOR BAKUNA PARA SA COVID 19!
- 7 #EmirateslovesPhilippines See less
- 8 FI: location
- 9 Author : FI helio, pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your
- 10 phone and get your appointment. From there, you will advised to your vaccine centre.
- 11 Author: F2 yes po

The subsequent extract was drawn from an Infographics image shared during the COVID-19 pandemic. This post depicted collaborative efforts between government organizations, various entities, and NGOs, united in the objective of disseminating vital information to the public regarding managing the pandemic. A prevalent activity during this period was the UAE's rollout of the vaccine drive. The post shows the information that Dubai is giving free vaccines for its residents and citizens. The author's original post contained comprehensive information, and the caption itself served as a comprehensive set of instructions and details for everyone on how to avail the vaccine. Analyzing the complete interactions and conversations between the author and their followers it is

clearly seen that there are obvious CA principal findings that are present.

Using extract 2, line by line analysis process, it began with the author's original post from line 1-7 with a caption of:

*Dubai is giving FREE Covid 19 vaccination! Get yours now! Download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA for your appointment. #NOappointmentNOentry
Thank you, UAE, for prioritizing the health and safety of citizens and residence alike!
And look! Truly, Emirates loves Philippines, sign at vaccination center has
Filipino translation!
CENTER FOR BAKUNA PARA SA COVID 19!*

With this caption, the author's goal is to keep the public well-informed with the necessary information pertinent to the announcement. As observed in the coming comments and replies that starts from line 8, follower 1, F1 commented asking for the location of the vaccine center. The author replied from the comment in line 9 and 10 using the same caption used from the first part of the original caption. In this sense, turn taking is observed. As discussed by (Moshavi, 2021), it is a recording of conversations wherein there is usually only one speaker at a time. In this scenario the author's original post allows its followers to respond and the conversation is open for questions or feedback. Though after the author responded it was observed that F1 did not have any follow up questions or even feedback. It appears that F1 was able to comprehend the author's repetition of the same caption.

Following on line 11, a comment of follower 2, F2 responded with a reply "yes po" that might mean that he/she understands a particular comment coming from either

another follower's comment or a response coming from the author which is unclear where it come from because a particular comment was deleted. The deletion of the comment might mean that there was a mistake or the one who posted it wants to remove it from the public's eye.

Continuation: Extract 2

```
12 F3 : Is there need for appointment ?  
13 Author: F3 yes po.  
14 F3 : Author San po pa share po ng link  
15 Author: F3 pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone. From  
16 there you will get directions on how to get your appointment. They will ask for the details of  
17 your EID.  
18 F3: Author thank you!!
```

Continuing the analysis of extract 2. From lines 12-18 a good example of Adjacency Pairs of CA was observed. Adjacency pairs are defined as a composition of two typically sequential turns, the first of which sets up an expectation for the second (Moshavi, 2021). With the definition stated, follower 3 F3, in line 12 ask the author if there is an appointment needed for the vaccination. From this question, author responded on line 13, saying “*yes po*” in which she directly answers F3’s query. Line 14 followed with a follow up question of F3 asking for the link of the appointment. From this question, the author responded with the same caption used from its original post which is the same answer it provided to F1 in the previous conversation from the first part of extract 2, with an inclusion of providing specific instructions and steps to follow on how to book an appointment. On line 18, F3 responded with a thank you that closes the loop of the conversation that completes the adjacency pair sequence. Observing from the exchange of replies from F3 and the author there was a clear understanding between the needs of the public and the way the author provided pertinent information. This interaction shows

that the organization was able to address concerns of the public in each piece of information that they are disseminating.

Figure 9

Manny Pacquiao screened in Dubai Festival City, a photo grabbed post from the Facebook page of the organization with interactions and exchange of comments and replies from followers.

Extract 3

1 Boxing Champ Manny Pacquiao display at Dubai Festival City certainly gives all the Filipinos
2 something to be proud of!
3 #EmiratesLovesPhilippines
4 Photo courtesy: [REDACTED]
5 F1: Nakaka proud ang maging Filipino!
6 Author: F1 thank you!
7 F2: Proud of our Boxing Champ Manny Pacquiao! Mabuhay ang Filipino!
8 Author: F2 produ!
9 F3:
10 Author: F3 thank you
11 F4:
12 Author: F4 thank you!

In this segment, the last extract for analysis was focused on a photo grabbed post of the boxing champion from the Philippines, Manny “Pacman” Pacquiao. The author posted and wrote a caption on lines 1-4 that pertains to the image that says:

Boxing Champ Manny Pacquiao display at Dubai Festival City certainly gives all the Filipinos something to be proud of!

#EmiratesLovesPhilippines

Photo courtesy: xxxxxxxxxxxx

This post signifies how the UAE supports the achievement of its residents. As a country where almost 200 plus nationalities are residing, Filipinos, as the fourth largest group in the Emirates, contribute to the overall economic growth of the nation and are considered as a group of talented, creative individuals. The image of Pacman, who represents the Filipino spirit and sportsmanship, was projected in one of the well-known hotel structures in Dubai which is a common activity to support any big achievement and

special occasion in the country. Having this content posted by the organization in their Facebook page allows the followers to appreciate and be thankful to the UAE and to feel how proud they are as a Filipino.

Analyzing the flow of conversation and interaction from the post, it is clearly observed that the pattern of CA that is present in most of the lines falls under the Turn Taking process, wherein the response from one speaker to another is basically considered as a normal utterance from a statement originally posted. In the context of online interactions such as this, the pattern is considered as an organized “*speech exchange system*” (Moshavi, 2021). From line 5 where follower 1, F1 commented with “*Nakaka proud ang maging Pilipino*” and the author replied right away with a thank you! This pattern of conversations continued from line 7 to 8 where F2, commented with “*Proud of our Boxing Champ Manny Pacquiao! Mabuhay ang Pilipino!*” and author replied with response of the word *produ* which is a spelling mistake that really means proud.

From the next line of conversation another form of comments and replies comes in and it is in the form of emoji images. Emojis are pictographs of faces, objects, and symbols with distinct styles, (Grannan, 2023). The use of the Philippine flag as a comment from the original post can signify different meanings but one thing is for sure that it symbolizes nationalistic emotions of how proud the follower is to be a Filipino. This kind of comment followed by another image form which is a GIF image of the Philippine flag. GIF file, which is short for Graphics Interchange Format, is an image file. Unlike other image formats, GIFs are frequently animated (Heinzman, 2022). Using this image file adds a creative emotion to the comment that signifies his/her love for the country

and being a Filipino himself. The author replied with a thank you! to appreciate F4s comment.

Continuation: Extract 3

13 F5:

14 Author: F5 thanks too

15 F5: Author You're welcome Sir

16 F6: This is Lit! Will visit UAE someday.

17 Author: F6 hope to see you here one day

18 F7: Mabuhay ang lahing Pilipino!

19 Author: F7 Mabuhay!

20 F8:

21 Author: F8

22 F9: A memorable day! Thank you UAE! #EmirateslovesPhilippines

23 Author: F9 that's right!

24 F10: Proud to be pinoy!

25 Author: F10 proud!

Continuing the analysis for extract 3, line 13 shows F5s comment with the usage of various emojis of the Philippine flag, shining pink heart, a red heart and smiley with hearts followed by a line mentioning how proud he/she is to Manny and wished him God bless as always. This line shows a high level of emotion towards the comment and symbolizes love for the country and to the personality that represents the nation. The author on line 14 replied with thanks and F5 responded right away with welcome. This sequence of conversation represents the Adjacency Pair of CA principal findings. From the next line in line 16, an interesting comment posted by F6 that says that the image is Lit which is short for the word “Literally”, this comment might mean a positive note from the F6 because the next line states that he/she wants to visit the UAE which signifies a positive tone of voice in his statement. The author responded right away with F6s comment by saying how they are to see him/her one day in the country. The conversation

shows a connection between the author and their followers. There was an organic connection through online conversation that supports how social media platforms can be an effective means of doing public relations activities.

From line 19-25 the same pattern of conversation of turn taking takes place where one comment and reply happens in the flow of conversation. All in all, this extract of conversation follows a point example of CA in action through online conversations. Overall, this analysis of all bracketed data in which the extracts utilized the line-by-line coding was able to produce an on-point representation of interpretation and meanings from the flow of conversation between the posted content of the author and their followers.

CHAPTER V

RESULTS

This chapter presents the research results of a qualitative conversation analysis (CA) of data extracted from the social media page of the non-profit organization in Dubai. This section will specifically present the results objectively to answer the specific research questions and to achieve the research aims of the study. This study tried to answer each research question such as the following:

- 1. What are the branding practices of a non-profit organization on social media platforms?*
- 2. What intent of non-profit organization do these branding practices accomplish?*

These research questions guided the qualitative research method using conversation analysis (CA) to analyze the sets of data. Based on the extract of the data gathered and a rigorous process of organizing it and identifying codes and themes, the findings were structured through common patterns extracted from the codes. The table below will show how each segment is interconnected to each other.

Table 1. Summary of codes, patterns, and analysis from extract 1

Extracts	Initial Analysis	Themes and Sub Themes	Codes that highlight the practices	Codes that pertain to what practice accomplish	Patterns in the codes	Overall Analysis
EXTRACT 1 Video Reel of Dubai Metro						
Caption- Author's Post: Is Dubai Metro CLEAN? #dubai #challenge #dubailiving #cleanestcity #dubaimetro	The author of the post is discussing whether the Dubai Metro is clean. While it appears clean and tidy, some followers believe it is not 100% clean. Another commenter mentions that despite having 1 million passengers daily, the metro is still considerably clean. Some followers and the author acknowledge that it may be hard to please everyone but stands by their opinion that there may still be bacteria present due to the crowded nature of the metro.	Urban environment: City cleanliness, Hygiene, Sanitation, Public Transportation	1. Disseminating information regarding Dubai's Public Transportation system like the Dubai Metro. 2. Promoting campaigns that inform the residents and citizens regarding the public transport system of the emirates. 3. Publishing content on the cleanliness and sanitation of the public transportation system. 4. Gathering public opinion using the social media platform.	1. Built a successful information dissemination to the public towards the Dubai Metro as a transportation system in the country. 2. Launched an effective strategy of communication through campaigns that promotes the overall outlook towards the Dubai Metro. 3. Produced informative social media content that communicates how the Dubai Metro's status of cleanliness and sanitation is. 4. Successfully gathered public opinion on their perceptions about the Dubai Metro that serves as a basis for evaluation and improvement for the government.	Based on the formulated codes, there were patterns and commonalities that highlight the practices and accomplishments of the organization in relation to their public relations activities. Such patterns are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information dissemination • Promotional campaigns • Gathering public opinions. 	The organization was able to disseminate information properly and effectively about the Dubai Metro's sanitation and cleanliness. They also successfully promote campaigns to inform residents and citizens about the benefits of using the public transport system. And was able to promote awareness and gather public opinion, and feedback using the social media as a platform.
F1: Germs/bacteria and viruses can't be seen in a simple wipe.It looks clean, tidy, but it's not 100% clean.						
Author to F1: I dunno about you, but the fact that we wiped it and no dirt? That kinda speaks volumes.						
F2 to Author: – Author it's hard to please sister 🍊						
F3 to F1: exactly						
F4 to F1: para sa public transpo with 1M passengers every day, it is considerably clean ghorl...and the video didnt mentioned that its "100% clean"...i bet even ur house isnt that clean...kelangan pa ba						

nagmicroscope sila?juskolord 🇦🇪 🇩🇪 🇩🇪						
F1 to F5: opinion ko, i won't change it because sabi mo. I'll post mine; you post yours. He looks clean, but I doubt that there will be no bacteria left behind, because of the crowd on board.						

The table offers a diverse range of codes that emphasize branding and public relations practices and their achievements. These were represented by codes which were formulated through a rigorous step by step coding of extracts and their meanings from the conversation flow. Such practices gave an important value to the organization's effort to provide service to the public. These practices were able to accomplish great outcomes where the organization was able to build successful information dissemination. They also launched an effective communication strategy and produced informative social media content that led to successful public participation through shared opinions. In summary, the organization effectively executed a high-quality, informative, and outcome-oriented campaign that resulted in meaningful public engagement. This campaign led to increased recognition and appreciation for the Dubai government's efforts in establishing a comprehensive public transportation system. The information gathered from the campaign has also been utilized to drive ongoing innovation and enhancement of services for the benefit of the nation's residents and citizens.

Table 2. Summary of codes, patterns, and analysis from extract 2

Extracts	Initial Analysis	Themes and Sub Themes	Codes that highlight the practices	Codes that pertain to what practice accomplish	Patterns in the codes	Overall Analysis
<p>EXTRACT 2 Infographics Photo of COVID19 Vaccination Center in Dubai</p> <p>Author's Post Dubai is giving FREE Covid 19 vaccination! Get yours now!Download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA for your appointment. #NOappointmentNOentryThank you, UAE, for prioritizing the health and safety of citizens and residence alike!And look! Truly, Emirates loves Philippines, sign at vaccination center has Filipino translation! CENTER FOR BAKUNA PARA SA COVID 19! #EmirateslovesPhilippines</p> <p>F1 to Author: location</p> <p>Author to F1 hello, pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone and get your appointment. From there, you will advised to your vaccine centre.</p> <p>Author to F2 yes po</p> <p>F3 to Author Is there need for appointment?</p> <p>Author to F3 yes po. F3 to Author San po pa share po ng link</p> <p>Author to F3 pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone. From there you will</p>	<p>The author informs readers that Dubai is offering free Covid-19 vaccinations and encourages them to download the DHA, MOHAP, or SEHA apps to schedule appointments.</p> <p>The author expresses gratitude to the UAE for prioritizing health and safety and mentions a sign in a vaccination center showing support for the Philippines.</p> <p>The author also answers</p>	<p>Global issues COVID-19, Gratitude, Healthcare, Localization</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Planning strategies to communicate the vaccination campaign of Dubai for the public. 2. Rolling out information to the public about the vaccination campaign of Dubai. 3. Guiding the public on the entire process of taking the vaccine. 4. Determining the effectivity of the information used for promoting the vaccination campaign of the government. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developed a strong way to communicate the vaccination campaign of the government for the benefit of the public. 2. Successfully informed the public regarding the vaccination campaign of Dubai. 3. Directed the public on the right ways on how to go about the process in availing the service of the government from appointment to vaccination. 4. Evaluated the effectivity of the campaign and its impact to the public. 	<p>Based on the formulated codes, there were patterns and commonalities that highlight the practices and accomplishments of the organization in relation to their public relations activities. Such patterns are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information dissemination • Communication strategies • Public information • Providing guidance 	<p>The organization successfully and effectively communicate the vaccination campaign of Dubai to the public. With its goal to roll out information about the campaign, they were able to guide the public on the process of taking the vaccine and determine the effectiveness of the information used to promote the campaign.</p>

get directions on how to get your appointment. They will ask for the details of your EID.	questions about appointment requirements and explains how to make appointments.					
F3 to Author thank you!!						
F4 to Author How to make appointments po						
Author to F4 pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone. From there you will get directions on how to get your appointment. They will ask for the details of your EID.						
F5 to Author its free payment po?						
Author to F5 free po siya. Just get the appointment.						
F5 to Author salamat po sa info 🍷🍷🍷						

From this summary, it shows a very interesting set of codes that highlight both the public relations practices and accomplishments of the organization. They developed a strong and effective communication process leading to an informed public and directing them in the right process of availing government services and overall, through this, the organization evaluated the effectivity of the campaign and its impact to the public. All in all, the organization's effort created an effective and useful strategy in communicating government initiatives and activities. Their collaboration exemplifies a perfect partnership between the government and non-profit organizations, both working together to support meaningful causes. Their shared goal is to enhance the quality of life for residents and citizens within the country, ultimately striving to create a better and more prosperous community.

Table 3. Summary of codes, patterns, and analysis from extract 3

Extracts	Initial Analysis	Themes and Sub Themes	Codes that highlight the practices	Codes that pertain to what practice accomplish	Patterns in the codes	Overall Analysis
<p>EXTRACT 3 Image of Manny Pacquiao projected at a Hotel Building in Dubai</p>	<p>The author is informing the readers about how Dubai as a city supports the achievements of its residents. Filipinos as one of the largest groups in the UAE has contributed a lot of amazing things in the Emirates. The author also promotes nationalism and Filipino pride. And commenters show how proud they are in being a Filipino being represented by Manny Pacquiao.</p>	<p>Pride: Celebrity endorsement, national pride, nationalism, Filipino Culture, Sports</p>	<p>1. Communicating the initiative of the country in promoting expatriates' success in different fields.</p> <p>2. Informing the Filipino expats on topics such as the achievement of Filipino icons using platform such as the social media.</p> <p>3. Promoting nationalism and love for the country.</p> <p>4. Igniting the audience sense of pride through the visual content published.</p>	<p>1. Positively communicated the UAE's initiative in promoting the success of expatriates in various fields such as sports.</p> <p>2. Effectively informed the Filipino expats on the success of fellow Kababayans using the social media platform.</p> <p>3. Filipinos in the UAE showed their love for the country and nationalism through comments and replies.</p> <p>4. Fleshed out audience interest and attention that promotes sense of pride from the visual content shared.</p>	<p>Based on the formulated codes, there were patterns and commonalities that highlight the practices and accomplishments of the organization in relation to their public relations activities. Such patterns are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information dissemination • Love for country • Sense of pride • Nationalism 	<p>In summary, the organizations' goal is to promote the success of Filipino expatriates using well-known personalities and how the UAE takes the initiative in doing it. The organization also promotes about achievements of Filipinos to foster nationalism, love for the country, and evoke a sense of pride through visual content using the social media.</p>
<p>Author: Boxing Champ Manny Pacquiao display at Dubai Festival City certainly gives all the Filipinos something to be proud of! #EmiratesLovesPhilippines</p>						
<p>F1 to Author: Nakaka proud ang maging Pilipino! 🇵🇭</p>						
<p>Author to F1 thank you!</p>						
<p>F2 to Author Proud of our Boxing Champ Manny Pacquiao! Mabuhay ang Pilipino!</p>						
<p>Author to F2 produ!</p>						
<p>F3 to Author 🇵🇭 🇵🇭 🇵🇭</p>						
<p>F4 to Author </p>						
<p>Author to F4 thank you!</p>						
<p>F5 to Author 🇵🇭 🇵🇭 🇵🇭 So proud to you lodi Manny Pacquiao Godbless you always ↓</p>						
<p>Author to F5 thanks too</p>						
<p>F5 to Author: You're welcome Sir ↓</p>						

F6 to Author: This is Lit! Will visit UAE someday. 🇦🇪						
Author to F6 hope to see you here one day						
F7 to Author: Mabuhay ang lahing Pilipino!						
F8 to Author: 🇵🇭 🇦🇪						
Author to F8 🇵🇭						
F9 to Author A memorable day! Thank you UAE!#EmirateslovesPhilippines						
Author to F9 that's right!						
F10 to Author: Proud to be pinoy!						
Author to F10 proud!						

Examining this comprehensive table, which offers a detailed and precise summary of information, it becomes evident that the organization effectively demonstrated a wide range of branding and public relations practices. These accomplishments are vividly represented by the meticulously formulated codes derived from the extracted data. The organization adeptly conveyed the UAE's endeavor to champion the achievements of its expatriates. They skillfully disseminated information to expatriates, highlighting the global accomplishments of their fellow countrymen and fostering a sense of collective pride and identity among all, evoking a shared sense of pride in being Filipino. These accomplishments serve as a great foundation in promoting love for the country and pushing the value of nationalism away from home. The successful implementation of these practices and achievements opens the potential for the emergence of further initiatives in various forms.

Digital Branding Practices

The analysis from the set of data yielded diverse sets of identified branding and public relations practices and how they are being conducted. The analysis of three distinct conversation extracts, each centered around different social media posts including a video reel, an infographic, and an image, has revealed a wide range of concepts. While some aspects were commonly observed, there were also intriguing nuances that lend significant meaning to the outcomes of this study, benefiting both the practices employed, the organization itself, and the engaged public. Each extract will serve as a reference point to delve deeper into the intricacies of the practices employed. By scrutinizing each activity through the lens of industry-specific terminologies, we enhance the utility of these findings, rendering them more valuable in contributing to the body of knowledge in this field. From the analysis it generated the following:

- 1. Social Media Content Publishing Strategy** – curating, posting, reposting content on public matters such as the cleanliness and sanitation of the public transportation system. As the study is all about social media use in branding practices, it basically provided the flow of publishing various forms of content. In the case of the Dubai Metro video reel content involves an interactive, creative, and unique way to deliver the information to the public. Through a combination of audio elements, dynamic visuals, and skillful editing techniques, the organization adeptly crafted content that actively engaged the public. This approach facilitated an inclusive conversation, enabling individuals to share their opinions and thoughts online. Another sample

is the infographics content published by the organization taken from the government's artwork. They were able to successfully inform the public about the vaccination program. Lastly the image of Manny Pacquiao projected in a hotel building façade, it sparked Filipino expatriate's emotions that produced a great sense of pride and love for the country. Publishing the content as an identified practice signifies that the organization carefully plans their curation of ideas, information that leads to producing quality content for the public's use. As indicated earlier, the organization demonstrates a keen understanding of the diverse nature of content. They have a clear awareness of which types of content have the potential to captivate the audience, sparking conversations and drawing them into the engagement process. From the published content, one example to cite is the thread of conversation from Manny Pacquiao's image. Because of the post which certainly reposted by other users as well, the public was able to showcase their feeling of their love for the country as discussed above. It ignites the t value of nationalism that results in heightening the level of sense of pride. Having this strong emotionally driven word put into action is an evidence that the content that was shared is a very effective means of communicating who the Filipinos are in a global landscape. Having the boxing legend as the icon that represents the Filipinos it brings the attention of the Filipino people to bring that joy and sense of pride that Filipino are great not only in the field of sports but also in all other fields of the expertise. From the extract shown below:

Lines 16-25 Excerpts from Extract 3

16 F6: This is Lit! Will visit UAE someday. 🇸🇦 🇵🇭
17 Author: F6 hope to see you here one day
18 F7: Mabuhay ang lahing Pilipino! 🇵🇭
19 Author: F7 Mabuhay!
20 F8: 🇸🇦 🇵🇭
21 Author: F8 😊
22 F9: A memorable day! Thank you UAE! #EmirateslovesPhilippines
23 Author: F9 that's right!
24 F10: Proud to be pinoy! 🇵🇭
25 Author: F10 proud!

It signifies how both the UAE and the Philippines worked together for the common good. Represented by flags icon and sets of replies of the followers which is diverse in nature but common in the meaning, it represents how effectively the organization communicated the goal of the content. The organization's approach not only fosters appreciation for both Filipinos and the UAE, but it also serves as an inclusive platform that celebrates the individual greatness of each Kababayan, welcoming everyone to share their unique contributions. Under the *social media content publishing strategy* one very significant specific practice that is identified is the existence of the:

1.1 Share and Repost Feature- It allows the audience to share and repost the same content to their networks, making the strategy more useful in a bigger crowd. Using the share option button feature on the page also helps the organization to disseminate information faster than ever. Looking at the images below 101 and 54 shares were made from both social media post.

These figures show a high rate of information dissemination, which is one of the common practices identified from the previous discussion about public

relations practices. This strategy of sharing the original post doesn't only provide wider reach but also it heightens the engagement and traction of the content. These scenarios create an excellent domino effect that yields favorable returns for the organization.

Figure 10

Caption screenshots from the infographics and image post of the organization in their Facebook Page with a highlight on the number of shares made by the public users and followers of the social media channel.

Information dissemination can be achieved through various means. With the aid of digital public relations practices, it has become easier to diversify the channels to reach a wider audience across the region. This approach has a significant impact on the effectiveness of content in engaging the receivers, i.e., the public. As a result of this strategy, it prompts specific actions from both the organization and the public, enabling them to harness the full potential of this feature.

- 2. Public Affairs Strategy** – This strategy relates to matters that affect the public directly. In the context of the social media post as a reference, the scenario of the Dubai Metro's cleanliness status and the COVID-19 vaccination program by the

UAE government was able to allow the PR practice to do the public affairs activity. Information dissemination, guiding the public on procedures and steps required and providing them assistance are some of the observed activities over the thread of conversations in the extract which is attached below:

Line 1 Excerpts from Extract 1

1 Author's Post: Is Dubai Metro CLEAN? #dubai #challenge #dubailiving #cleanestcity #dubaimetro

Lines 1-5 from Extract 2

1 Author's Post Dubai is giving FREE Covid 19 vaccination! Get yours now!

2 Download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA for your appointment. #NOappointmentNOentry

3 Thank you, UAE, for prioritizing the health and safety of citizens and residence alike!

4 And look! Truly, Emirates loves Philippines, sign at vaccination center has Filipino translation!

5 CENTER FOR BAKUNA PARA SA COVID 19!

The extract depicting the organization's original post serves as a prime example of basic information dissemination. Furthermore, it effectively represents the promotion of a campaign, aligning with one of the identified practices discussed earlier. As public affairs relate to any public activities, this scenario allows the organization to take part in dealing with the public; not only by informing them but also by educating them. In the context of our extracts, the public were educated by simply giving them specific words and statements that shows public affairs involvement of the organization. Followers were educated through the strategic use of hashtags that emphasized the significance of specific words, such as #NoappointmentNoentry. While this seemingly simple example might be overlooked by many, its impact on the program's execution is substantial.

The organization's usage of such hashtags brings them to the

understanding that they need to reiterate information to educate the people and to guide them on various information that is helpful for them.

Specific activities were also identified under this category which makes the result more meaningful and provides exact information from each extract used as a reference from the analysis.

2.1 Information Dissemination - disseminating information regarding Dubai's Public Transportation system like the Dubai Metro. From this first identified branding practice it was observed that from the original post of the author wherein they instigate a conversation by asking a specific question: *"Is Dubai Metro Clean?"* opens the door to its followers to start giving their opinions. In the exchange of conversation, the practice of information dissemination rises up. With the extract attached:

Lines 1-5 Excerpts from Extract 1

- 1 Author's Post: Is Dubai Metro CLEAN? #dubai #challenge #dubailiving #cleanestcity #dubaimetro
- 2 F1 - Germs/bacteria and viruses can't be seen in a simple wipe.
- 3 It looks clean, tidy, but it's not 100% clean.
- 4 Author: F1 I dunno about you, but the fact that we wiped it and
- 5 no dirt? That kinda speaks volumes.

In response to a seemingly negative comment challenging the caption, the author provided a reply that included basic information on how they assessed Dubai Metro's cleanliness. Despite the follower's personal skepticism, the author skillfully addressed the concern, offering a balanced and confident response. The overall exchange from post to replies and comments shows that information dissemination is present and one of the discovered branding practices involved in the process.

2.2 Public information- In contrast to the previous practice in extract 1, the statement regarding the vaccination campaign in Dubai exhibits a similar nature. However, there is a distinct approach in this scenario, as the organization directly imparts instructions and information to the public. The communication is straightforward and delivered in a concise and precise manner.

Amidst the pandemic, the post was generated to essentially disseminate instructions to the public, a situation that unfolded globally. However, what sets this apart from others, based on my personal experience and observation, is the effective collaboration between the government and the organization in providing comprehensive information to the public. They both use available platforms and even develop new ones to help the public become more aware of such practices, programs, and initiatives for them. Observing from the extract below:

Lines 1-7 Excerpts from Extract 2

- 1 Author's Post Dubai is giving FREE Covid 19 vaccination! Get yours now!
- 2 Download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA for your appointment. #NOappointmentNOentry
- 3 Thank you, UAE, for prioritizing the health and safety of citizens and residence alike!
- 4 And look! Truly, Emirates loves Philippines, sign at vaccination center has Filipino translation!
- 5 CENTER FOR BAKUNA PARA SA COVID 19!
- 7 #EmirateslovesPhilippines See less

The organization skillfully crafted the caption to succinctly convey the essential information, effectively guiding the followers to comprehend the necessary details needed for them to access the government service available for the public's benefit. Highlighting the names of each government organizations app is a means to point out that it is indeed a successful way to inform the public. The usage of all

caps in a “taglish” Tagalog – English line CENTER FOR BAKUNA PARA SA COVID 19 signified that it also personalized and adjusted as per the demographics of the users and followers of the social media page. Informing the public in this scenario shows different ways that organizations exert their effort to give all the important details as again they mediate the public and the government to one another.

2.3 Guiding the public -By guiding the public on the proper procedures to follow for availing government services, ranging from scheduling appointments to receiving vaccinations, the organization effectively achieved its objective. Transitioning from basic information dissemination to providing specific instructions, the organization successfully fulfilled this goal.

As evidenced by the repeated use of the same caption in response to queries, it becomes evident that the organization is committed to ensuring clear guidance for all those seeking information. In the extract below:

Lines 12-18 Excerpts from Extract 2

12 F3 : Is there need for appointment ?
13 Author: F3 yes po.
14 F3 : Author San po pa share po ng link
15 Author: F3 pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone. From
16 there you will get directions on how to get your appointment. They will ask for the details of
17 your EID.
18 F3: Author thank you!!

The author responded to one of the follower’s question about appointments. They made sure that aside from sharing the same information they added a few

lines to give specific instructions for the public to follow. It shows step-by-step guidance provided by the organization which is a very good move for them to go the extra mile. The service rendered by the organization to the public is not just to guide them but also to lead them to avail themselves of the government service successfully. By having this steps followed by the public, the people themselves can share the same instructions to others to follow the same procedure and it makes the information dissemination more impactful and faster for everyone.

3. **Generating public opinion** - using the social media platform. This practice represents the exciting segment of the diversity of what I call the “*Word War*” in a sense that it is very evident that the followers bring their different opinions and emotions on the table. The word wart shows how each follower agrees and disagrees with the replies and comments of fellow followers and even the author. It sounded a bit negative when following the thread but clearly provides a perfect example of gathering public opinion.

Lines 2-3 Excerpts from Extract 1

2 F1 - Germs/bacteria and viruses can't be seen in a simple wipe.
3 It looks clean, tidy, but it's not 100% clean.

Lines 6-11 Excerpts from Extract 1

6 F2 - Author it's hard to please sister 😊
7 F3 - F1 exactly
8 F4 - F1 para sa public transpo with 1M passengers everyday, it is
9 considerably clean ghorl...and the video didnt
10 mentioned that its "100% clean"...i bet even ur house isnt that clean...kelangan pa ba
11 nagmicroscope sila?juskolord 🤔🤔🤔

Lines 12-15 Excerpts from Extract 1

12 F1 - F5 opinion ko, i won't change it because sabi mo. I'll post

13 mine; you post yours.

14 He looks clean, but I doubt that there will be no bacteria left behind, because of the crowd

15 on board.

Referring to the excerpts provided earlier, it is evident that a diverse range of ideas and opinions, often accompanied by emotions, is present. From the organization's standpoint, they have effectively accomplished the task of gathering public opinions. Through a simple caption that poses a specific question about a relevant topic, one that allows nearly all followers to engage in the conversation, the organization successfully elicited a multitude of perspectives on the subject.

Public opinion is an essential part of branding practices as it allows people to have a voice to be heard. Their comments serve as a foundation for enhancing the delivery of services by both the organization and the government.

- 4. Publicity Strategy** – considered as one of the common ways to do PR, its procedure is providing the public with meaningful information they can use to know about a certain organization, program, and initiative. The goal of this is for the public to have a favorable perception towards it. In the context of the extract and social media content this description falls on the scenario of the Dubai Metro video reels post and the Manny Pacquiao image. Using the extract below:

Lines 8-11 Excerpts from Extract 1

8 F4 - F1 para sa public transpo with 1M passengers everyday, it is

9 considerably clean ghorl...and the video didnt

10 mentioned that its "100% clean"...i bet even ur house isnt that clean...kelangan pa ba

11 nagmicroscope sila?juskolord 🤔🤔🤔

Taking from this extract, it shows the reply of one of the followers answering another reply of another follower. The response shows a good way to describe the Dubai Metro's cleanliness status. This response shows a good perception of the public towards the organization. Her way of pointing out the cleanliness of the public transportation signifies that the social media content posted by the organization is effective in the sense that she also supported the content by opposing the comment of the other follower.

Lines 16-25 Excerpts from Extract 3

16 F6: This is Lit! Will visit UAE someday. 😊🇵🇭
17 Author: F6 hope to see you here one day
18 F7: Mabuhay ang lahing Pilipino! 🇵🇭
19 Author: F7 Mabuhay!
20 F8: 🇵🇭🇮🇪
21 Author: F8 😊
22 F9: A memorable day! Thank you UAE! #EmirateslovesPhilippines
23 Author: F9 that's right!
24 F10: Proud to be pinoy! 🇵🇭
25 Author: F10 proud!

From this extract, as this content promotes a particular personality, it is directly showing a publicity approach. Using the approach, it shows that the public agrees with the personalities representation of becoming a successful Filipino. It extends its publicity towards the entire representation of being a Filipino and shows how proud Filipinos are. With words of compliments and thanks, the publicity approach as part of the public relations practice creates an effective means of communicating the content in social media as it allows public engagement. Specific activities have been identified under this strategy, which will enable the extraction of precise information from each of the extracts used as references in the analysis.

4.1 Strategic planning – developing a communication strategy for the vaccination campaign of the government for the benefit of the public. Taking from the original post and caption shared by the organization already represents how they take things seriously. The caption itself already overarches all the required information to let the public know what is needed and what is required. The focal point of attention was the identical replies shared by the organization as they responded to the public's questions seeking clarification. The extract below shows this scenario.

Lines 1-10 Excerpts from Extract 2

```
1 Author's Post Dubai is giving FREE Covid 19 vaccination! Get yours now!  
2 Download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA for your appointment. #NOappointmentNOentry  
3 Thank you, UAE, for prioritizing the health and safety of citizens and residence alike!  
4 And look! Truly, Emirates loves Philippines, sign at vaccination center has Filipino translation!  
5 CENTER FOR BAKUNA PARA SA COVID 19!  
7 #EmirateslovesPhilippines See less  
8 Fl: location  
9 Author : Fl hello, pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your  
10 phone and get your appointment. From there, you will advised to your vaccine centre.
```

Clearly, the organization aimed to emphasize and reinforce the information, without making any alterations, as the caption directly conveyed the necessary details. It's a common practice for people to sometimes overlook information, leading to questions and, consequently, confusion, even when the information is readily available. The instruction of the organization to download different apps will lead the public to book an appointment to avail the vaccine and it shows a strong means to create a powerful communication strategy. Repeating things again and again in this context creates power and authority over the instruction and towards its receivers.

4.2 Campaign Promotion – The non-profit organization is promoting a campaign aimed at informing both residents and citizens about the public transport system in the Emirates. One of the common PR practices globally is producing campaigns to strengthen the process of information dissemination. The analysis resulted from having this practice as the overall goal of the social media post is promoting a campaign that allows stakeholders to take part in the conversation which is a good communication practice. A non-profit organization's main goal is to keep the public informed and to mobilize them to take part from these campaigns and initiatives. It is very evident in the flow of conversation that followers do participate and it's a great move to show how the campaign promotion takes effect.

Lines 6-11 Excerpts from Extract 1

6 F2 - Author it's hard to please sister 🤔
7 F3 - F1 exactly
8 F4 - F1 para sa public transpo with 1M passengers everyday, it is
9 considerably clean ghorl...and the video didnt
10 mentioned that its "100% clean"...i bet even ur house isnt that clean...kelangan pa ba
11 nagmicroscope sila7juskolord 🤔🤔🤔

The feedback from every follower with different points of view and emotions attached to every comments shows that the campaign is truly effective as they were able to ignite the emotions of the followers. This scenario involves everyone participating in a more focused and specific process of effectively executing the campaign.

4.3 Programs and initiatives communication – communicating and promoting expatriates' success in different fields. UAE is a country with residents from almost 200 nationalities. Each group plays an important role in developing the economy of the country in different sectors and industries. Having this image posted as social media content paved the way to see that the UAE and its government promotes the success of its expatriate groups. The organization's motive to post the image significantly creates a good promotion on the move of the government and the happiness of the Filipino community to celebrate the success of one its icons. From the extract of conversation below:

Lines 1-3 Excerpts from Extract 3

```
1 Boxing Champ Manny Pacquiao display at Dubai Festival City certainly gives all the Filipinos  
2 something to be proud of!  
3 #EmiratesLovesPhilippines
```

The organization exhibits how the UAE government supports the success of its expatriates' groups. Projecting the image of Manny Pacquiao that represents the Filipino community in the UAE is a representation of how appreciative the Emiratis are to the Filipinos. This moves from the government and by the organization to share it to the social media platform allows great engagement to the public. It provides an opportunity for the public, particularly the Filipinos, to share their utmost gratitude to the country and its government for giving an avenue to showcase how great Filipinos are in different fields and industry. Through the caption in the extract, the organization ensures that readers understand that Filipinos collectively share the same sentiments about the image displayed on a large building façade.

4.4 Campaign evaluation - evaluating the effectiveness of the campaign and its impact on the public. A crucial aspect of the practices that ensured their effectiveness was the evaluation of the entire applied approach. This identified practice is very significant to the overall delivery of all services, as it encapsulates the beginning and the end of the program. From the responses of the followers, their questions are being answered. The satisfaction and expressions of joy and gratitude evident in the followers' replies indicate the significant effort exerted by the organization and its members. From the extract below:

Lines 20-14 Excerpts from Extract 2

20 Author: F4 pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone. From there
21 you will get directions on how to get your appointment. They will ask for the details of your EID.
22 F5: Author its free payment po?
23 Author: F5 free po siya. Just get the appointment.
24 F5: Author salamat po sa info 🙏🙏🙏

There was a clear and evident effectiveness of the campaign as the followers were able to thank the organization for sharing specific information. Having smiley face emojis attached to the words added value and showed that the person really appreciated the effort. Though the interpretation of the effectiveness of the campaign merely focused on the extract, it just made a point that having people involved in the process even with just feedback matters a lot. Like the previous extract in the initial social media post, there is a notable impact when an organization encourages its stakeholders to engage in open conversations, fostering open innovation and enhancing the quality-of-service delivery to the public.

Digital Branding Accomplishments

To measure the effectiveness of the identified branding practices of the non-profit organization through public relations, the ultimate source of information is from its accomplishments. As a brand, they aim to communicate and to cover different types of stories that would reach the hearts and interests of people in the Emirates and around the world. Aligned with these objectives, it substantiates various identified strategies, in conjunction with the non-profit organization's approach, which subsequently culminates in a series of achieved accomplishments. Accomplishments are both tangible and intangible outcomes from a successful execution of the practices identified. And from the previous discussion of the results of branding practices through public relations, the next section will present the specific accomplishments gained.

1. Accomplishments of Social Media Content Publishing Strategy – as mentioned, content publishing comes from successful content creation with diverse forms of media content such as video, image, audio, and other media elements. From the analysis, the results showed that the non-profit organization intended to:

1.1 Curate informative social media content. Regarding the Dubai Metro video reel, the content was meticulously crafted, encompassing visuals, sounds, script, camera angles, shots, and comprehensive post-production techniques. This amalgamation signifies the informative essence of social media content.

Being informative is not only about the word information shared but it is also about the overall look and feel of the produced material. In this case, the quality of the video presented ticks all the boxes to make it an effective social media content. To support this claim, the overall thread of the conversation closes the loop as interactions and organic conversation arise.

CONVERSATIONS: EXTRACT 1

1 Author's Post: Is Dubai Metro CLEAN? #dubai #challenge #dubailiving #cleanestcity #dubaimetro
2 F1 - Germs/bacteria and viruses can't be seen in a simple wipe.
3 It looks clean, tidy, but it's not 100% clean.
4 Author: F1 I dunno about you, but the fact that we wiped it and
5 no dirt? That kinda speaks volumes.
6 F2 - Author it's hard to please sister 😏
7 F3 - F1 exactly
8 F4 - F1 para sa public transpo with 1M passengers everyday, it is
9 considerably clean ghorl...and the video didnt
10 mentioned that its "100% clean"...i bet even ur house isnt that clean...kelangan pa ba
11 nagmicroscope sila?juskolord 🤔🤔🤔
12 F1 - F5 opinion ko, i won't change it because sabi mo. I'll post
13 mine; you post yours.
14 He looks clean, but I doubt that there will be no bacteria left behind, because of the crowd
15 on board.

This whole extract of conversation is the mirror of an accomplished and effective social media content as it informs, educates, ignites emotions, and allows people to take part in a conversation that matters to them, the non-profit organization, and the government.

1.2 Capture a wider reach of audience through share and repost feature.

Because of the share and repost feature of the social media platform, the organization was able to reach a wider audience and was able to create large number of engagements in their social media. The thread of conversation is the

proof that the reach of the post gathered a lot of people participating in the conversation and taking part to act on specific matters of concern.

2. Accomplishments of Public Affairs Strategy – from the previous discussion, public affairs were described as a PR activity wherein they related to matters about the public. Such activities involve information dissemination and public information. In the context of the research and its extracts. From this strategy, the non-profit organization intended to:

2.1 Broadcast information for the public- Through the social media post of the video reel of the Dubai Metro with the catchy caption, interactive and creative script delivery and fantastic post-processing applied in the video, the organization was able to catch the attention of the viewers. As described in the first section of the results chapter, the audience took time to share their opinions and views by sharing their feedback and comments upon the question raised. Though, as also mentioned, the thread of the conversation doesn't feel 100% positive as there is feedback that did not agree with most of the comments, still the post is considered effective. The organization was able to draw out what is inside the public's head and what they feel. Observing from one of the excerpts from the extract:

Lines 12-15 Excerpts from Extract 1

12 F1 - F5 opinion ko, i won't change it because sabi mo. I'll post

13 mine; you post yours.

14 He looks clean, but I doubt that there will be no bacteria left behind, because of the crowd

15 on board.

The extract illustrates a dissenting viewpoint from a commenter in response to another comment, reflecting the result of a fruitful information dissemination, as indicated by the ensuing reactions. The organization's posts triggered one follower to itemize his/her opinion towards the information shared through a question raised and stemmed into different ideas and information.

2.2 Communicate human stories of success- With a very good visual image of Manny Pacquiao in a big space of a hotel building façade. The caption and the responses of the public say it all. A human story of success was communicated, and they were able to see the victory of their fellow Kababayan as this icon represents the entire Filipino community abroad. It evokes happiness and shows the true meaning of how proud they are being Filipino, and this emotion leads to show their love for the country and foster the value of nationalism through comments and replies. These scenarios both produced a positive sense of emotions from the public and signify a positive outlook toward life and towards their country. As an accomplishment, it embodies the true meaning of nationalism. The Filipino expats were able to bring out their undying love for the country and was ignited through the post of the organization. The extract proved this results as it shows from the thread of the conversation.

Lines 7-13 Excerpts from Extract 3

7 F2: Proud of our Boxing Champ Manny Pacquiao! Mabuhay ang Pilipino!

8 Author: F2 produ!

9 F3:

10 Author: F3 thank you

11 F4:

12 Author: F4 thank you!

13 F5: So proud to you lodi Manny Pacquiao Godbless you always 🙏

The extract signifies all the love and emotions of the followers. This entire thread exemplifies the organization's successful achievement in evoking a sense of joy and pride within the public. Being an OFW, seeing that represents your nation is one of the move that brings ecstatic emotion and excitement. This activity of the government communicated by the organization is not new but having this consistently still moves the people's emotion and it made them prouder and happier to be a Filipino.

2.3 Instruct the public - The non-profit organization was able to instruct the public on the step-by-step process on how to avail the vaccine program of the government. From their original post and captions it provided the public basic and on-point information. Looking at the extract it will describe these first three accomplishments mentioned:

Lines 1-7 Excerpts from Extract 2

- 1 Author's Post Dubai is giving FREE Covid 19 vaccination! Get yours now!
- 2 Download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA for your appointment. #NOappointmentNOentry
- 3 Thank you, UAE, for prioritizing the health and safety of citizens and residence alike!
- 4 And look! Truly, Emirates loves Philippines, sign at vaccination center has Filipino translation!
- 5 CENTER FOR BAKUNA PARA SA COVID 19!
- 7 #EmirateslovesPhilippines See less

The long caption giving information to get a free vaccine with instructions on how to go about the vaccination process helps the public to easily avail themselves of the vaccine. Though there are questions, the organization was still able to help them by responding to their comments and repeatedly mentioning the same caption from the original post along with added information to make the responses a tailored fit for the question. See below extract.

Lines 14-18 Excerpts from Extract 2

- 14 F3 : Author San po pa share po ng link
- 15 Author: F3 pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone. From
- 16 there you will get directions on how to get your appointment. They will ask for the details of
- 17 your EID.
- 18 F3: Author thank you!!

The extract shows an effort from the organization to respond to the public's queries and clarifications regarding the vaccination process. As they reply they make sure that significant information will be mentioned to guide the public further. Based on the thread of conversation it is observable that they were able to successfully do it. The instructions of downloading various government mobile applications signify that the organization leads the public on to the next step to be able to reach the registration and access the government service.

As this vaccination campaign was a demand for all people during those time, the organization made sure that each line stated in their post and comments mattered to the people and will provide valuable information for them.

2.4 Converge public opinion - From the previous discussion this accomplishment is one of the biggest highlights as it shows the connection between the organization and the public. The public is the center of attention here. Threads of the conversation zoom in on the different opinions stated by the public, agreements and disagreements are there, but both serve as a measure for an impactful social media post. Mobilizing the public in any means, like taking part in the conversation, is a true accomplishment as this will open doors for other ideas that can be helpful in the same topic being discussed or even useful for other public concerns. Consequently, public opinion is considered a fair strategy in the public relations sphere as it will not allow bias in decision-making and evaluation of the programs initiated. It creates a balanced look at the situation and provides an easy way to see things the way they should be seen.

3. Accomplishments of Publicity Strategy – Publicity’s goal is for the public to have a favorable perception towards people, organizations, programs, and initiatives. Through these identified PR practices and other activities related to them, the organization was able to:

3.1 Produce means to communicate government programs – In the context of the COVID-19 vaccination program of the government, the non—profit organization was able to produce means to communicate the initiative. The public’s response is overwhelming as each of them really ask instructions that leads them on taking the vaccine successfully. This scenario shows that the communication strategy conducted by the organization for this content was indeed effective. The extract below shows the results.

Lines 12-18 Excerpts from Extract 2

12 F3 : Is there need for appointment ?
13 Author: F3 yes po.
14 F3 : Author San po pa share po ng link
15 Author: F3 pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone. From
16 there you will get directions on how to get your appointment. They will ask for the details of

3.2 Communicate the UAE's initiative for expatriates- Through the social media post the organization was able to communicate the initiative of the UAE government in promoting the success of its expatriates. This results from a huge acceptance and appreciation of the public as they witness this kind of move from the government. From the extract below:

Lines 20-22 Excerpts from Extract 3

20 F8: 🇵🇭 🇦🇪
21 Author: F8 😊
22 F9: A memorable day! Thank you UAE! #EmirateslovesPhilippines

It shows that the public well appreciated the effort of the government. Their responses show a positive message as they thank the UAE. The use of emojis

and icons in the thread signifies their emotion towards their comments which means a lot and represented a great accomplishment for the organization.

3.3 Assess the campaign - This accomplishment was derived from the responses of the public in the thread. Those lines saying thank you are proof of a useful campaign in which the public appreciates the effort of the organization to provide guidance and instruction for them. Observing the post, it's evident that even though the information is straightforward, there are still individuals who ask questions that have obvious answers within the post. However, the organization's role is to address and accommodate their concerns, as seen in the extract below:

Lines 12-17 Excerpts from Extract 2

12 F3 : Is there need for appointment ?

13 Author: F3 yes po.

14 F3 : Author San po pa share po ng link

15 Author: F3 pls download DHA, MOHAP or SEHA on your phone. From

16 there you will get directions on how to get your appointment. They will ask for the details of

Assessing the campaign using the responses of the public might seem very shallow but indeed the public's response says a lot. Short lines are meaningful, these words of appreciation mean they understand, and they were able to grasp what was discussed. Surely after following the organization's instructions, they were able to avail the vaccine through following the basic information stated from the Facebook page post.

Overall, this social media post exemplifies a successful collaboration between the organization and the government, working for the benefit of the public who are the ultimate beneficiaries of the program. Through effective public relations practices, the organization and the government have jointly achieved these accomplishments.

Discussion

The specific findings stated were able to address both the research aim and the research questions and provided an argument that the branding practices of the non-profit organization was able to accomplish its intent using social media. As previously discussed in the literature review section, existing studies found out the same insights as this study, but the difference is this research was able to fulfill the goal through seeing the lens of effectively using the social media platform to let the public be part of the conversation and to act upon it. These bodies of knowledge encompass the concepts that have emerged in this research. It was very evident that all of them worked together for a common purpose and goal which is to serve the public to the best of their ability and resources. The findings distinctly revealed a diverse range of activities undertaken by the non-profit organization for various government programs and initiatives, and they successfully achieved their objectives for each of these activities. In summary, the recognized achievements of the organization, resulting from their branding efforts facilitated by public relations and executed through social media platforms, portray a remarkable synergy between them, the government, and the public. A distinct image emerges, showcasing dedicated teamwork, unwavering passion, and effective collaboration across all dimensions of a great teamwork between them, the government,

and the public. There was a clear picture of effort, passion, and collaboration in all aspects.

The non-profit organization encapsulates its achievements by assessing public visibility, opinions, and sentiments, formulating communication strategies, executing multi-channel communication initiatives, integrating communication with marketing efforts, fostering mutual communication, and crucially, cultivating a favorable rapport between the public and the organization. This study's findings reaffirm that due to their branding endeavors via public relations, the non-profit organization as a brand exemplifies the essence of leadership, integrity, equity, and camaraderie.

CHAPTER VI

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter will conclude the study by summarizing the key research findings in relation to the research aim and research questions, as well as the value and contribution thereof. It will also provide opportunities for future research endeavors within the same sphere of industry and topic.

Summary

This research aims to identify the branding practices of a non-profit organization in Dubai through public relations in a digital platform and to discover their accomplishments based on the identified practices. A qualitative research approach is employed, specifically utilizing ethnomethodology as the research framework, to facilitate the analysis of data extracted from social media content posts and interactions between the non-profit organization and its followers. Conversation analysis (CA) which is focused on the center of talk interaction was utilized to deeply analyze the set of data. From various segmented conversation flows within the social media content posts of the non-profit organization, distinct codes were generated to denote specific practices and achievements.

Based on these codes a common pattern was identified that significantly represents the branding practices and strategies such as: (1) social media content publishing strategy (2) public affairs strategy (3) publicity strategy. These identified practices include sub activities that create a more diverse means to communicate what the organization is all about and what they can do for the benefit of the public. In terms of the accomplishments stemmed from these practices the organization was able to do the following: (1) curate informative social media content (2) capture a wider reach of audience through share and repost feature (3) broadcast information for the public (4) communicate human stories of success (5) instruct the public (6) converge public opinion (7) produce means to communicate government programs (8) communicate the UAE's initiative for expatriates and lastly (9) assess the different campaign. Overall, these results show that the non-profit organization's branding practices and accomplishments play a significant role in the life of the community, as well as being the bridge that mediates the gap between the public and the government.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings of this study were able to provide valuable insights in the practice of media and communications in the field of non-profit organizations. It reveals that there are effective strategies being used by the organization to disseminate information to the public. There are also successful campaigns being produced by the organization to help the government to communicate their programs and initiatives to its residents and citizens. Also, they were able to allow the public to be part of the communication process by giving them a platform to share their opinions using the social

media and finally, it shows that the country shows love and acceptance to the expats living in the country by providing them platforms to support their endeavors.

Implications

This study can impact future research endeavors that can benefit from the research findings by using a different type of organization setting and a larger number of research samples. Additionally, future studies could also investigate the possibility of using the same concept but having a specific identification of the organization to create a more organic result. Overall, the findings of this study contribute to the ever-growing field of communications, particularly the public relations industry. As such, these findings will help other communications practitioners to evaluate the effectiveness of their public relations programs and how they will achieve their program objectives to serve their communities and their stakeholders.

Recommendations

This section of the study will present recommendations for three specific area: (1) theoretical, (2) methodological, and (3) practical.

For future research

As this study utilized a qualitative research method and used a research framework it is recommended for future researchers to:

1. Replicate the study by utilizing a theoretical framework instead of a research framework. By doing this it will allow to discover a new set of various branding practices of an organization using a different methodological approach.

2. Use research theories to back up the future study of the same field but focusing on a private organization.
3. Use quantitative research methods to specifically quantify respondents' opinions and beliefs on different branding practices of a non-profit organization.

For public relations industry practitioners

Through this study it is highly recommended that public relations practitioners constantly measure the effectiveness of each branding practice they perform within their organization setting and to specifically create means to measure the level of their accomplishments whether they successfully achieve it or not.

For non-profit organizations

It is recommended that non-profit organizations should adopt a scheme that will constantly provide sets of standards of best practices in their branding and public relations activities to support their growth as an organization. This will help them to continuously support the needs of the public by producing effective programs and initiatives to the public in support of the government's mandate.

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